

Scale-Invariant Variations of Max Regret (Longer Version)

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Abstract. Max regret is frequently used, in situations when there is uncertainty about a user preference model in a multi-objective optimisation problem, as a measure of how close an alternative is to being necessarily optimal. It is used in a termination condition for a dialogue with a user, and for recommending a compromise solution, and in different ways of generating informative queries. In this paper we consider linear user preference models based on simple weighted sums of the objectives. Unfortunately, max regret lacks a desirable scale-invariance property: changing the units (or the linear scaling) of the objectives can significantly alter the relative values of max regret between alternatives, even though the choice of units is often somewhat arbitrary. In this paper we define variations of max regret in which the regret, of an alternative given a particular user model, is divided by a function expressing a range of utility values. This leads to scale-invariance, and maintains important properties of max regret such as translation-invariance (in contrast with max relative regret). We show how linear programming and extreme points algorithms can be used for computation.

This is a longer version of the ECAI 2024 paper [24].

1 Introduction

We consider a common kind of preference model for multi-objective optimisation: a weighted sum based on a vector of weights, and we are considering situations in which there is only partial information about the weights vector, leading to a set \mathcal{W} of compatible weights vectors. With respect to a user preference model (represented by a weights vector), the regret of an alternative α is the difference between the best utility of any alternative and the utility obtained with α . The max regret is the maximum over all weights vectors in \mathcal{W} .

Max regret is a very valuable tool in interactive preference optimisation, where we want to find an optimal alternative for the user, based on iterative querying. It is used in a termination condition for the interaction: stopping when the minimax regret is at most some small positive number ϵ , indicating that there is an alternative which is close to being necessarily optimal, i.e., optimal with respect to each element in \mathcal{W} . When the interaction finishes, the minimax regret alternative can be recommended. It is also used for generating informative queries.

Max regret has several good properties that enable these tasks. The max regret of an alternative α is non-negative, and is zero if and only if α is necessarily optimal. When additional information (such as the

user's answers to queries) reduces \mathcal{W} , the max regret of each alternative never increases. Max regret satisfies an important translation-invariance property: adding a constant vector to all the utility vectors does not change the values of max regret. Computation of max regret can be achieved either with linear programming or with extreme points methods.

For max regret to be always finite one needs to bound the set \mathcal{W} of weights vectors; one common way of doing this is to only consider weights vectors that are normalised in the sense that the weights sum to 1. However, if one assumes a different way of normalising the weights then this can give a very different result.

A related problem for max regret is that it is not invariant to changes of scales (or units) of the objectives. However, the particular units chosen for an objective can be fairly arbitrary; and, as shown in [23], the chosen units can make a big difference to relative values of max regret, and can lead to a different alternative minimising max regret. (In fact, changing the units has the same effect as changing the normalisation method.) This shows a basic weakness, and a lack of robustness of max regret.

In [23], methods are derived for ameliorating this problem by considering families of scales. However, a more fundamental and neater approach is to change the definition of max regret. One measure is max relative regret, which maximises the ratio between regret and the maximum utility. Although this is scale-invariant, it loses the translation-invariance property.

Our new approach in this paper is to instead divide regret by a different function D , leading to what we call *max D -relative regret*. We focus especially on four functions that all relate to a range of different utility values over the set of alternatives. We show that this leads to scale-invariance, as well as maintaining important properties of max regret, such as translation-invariance, and monotonicity with respect to the set \mathcal{W} of weights vectors. The more complex form of the measure complicates the computational task; however, we derive both linear programming methods and extreme points methods for computation.

Related Work: Simple linear preference models are a commonly applied special case of Multi-Attribute Utility Theory (MAUT) [14, 10, 7] for multi-objective reasoning. As a model for unknown user preferences, using a weighted average with unknown weights, they have been used for instance in [8, 6, 20, 15, 13, 9, 3]. Max regret [16] is frequently used for decision problems with partial knowledge of the user preference model, for recommending alternatives, in generating queries, and in deciding when to terminate the user interaction, see e.g., [22, 4, 5, 12, 2, 21]. This paper is especially motivated

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by the work in [23], which pointed out the lack of scale-invariance of max regret, and developed approaches for reasoning with families of rescalings, as well as characterising situations in which the ratio of the max regret of two alternatives can be arbitrarily large (for extreme scalings). The variations of max regret defined here in Sections 3 and 4 are of a related form to max relative regret [11, 1], which, as mentioned above, is scale-invariant but not translation-invariant (see the end of Section 2 below).

The remainder of the paper is structured as follows. In Section 2 we describe the formal setting and max regret, along with issues of rescaling. Section 3 describes the new variation of max regret, based on considering the ratio of regret and the value of a function D , and shows some fundamental general properties. Section 4 considers four particular choices of the function D . In Section 5 we prove that like max regret, translation-invariance is satisfied by the four functions, and Section 6 shows that scale-invariance is satisfied, in contrast with max regret. Section 7 considers a computational approach based on the use of extreme points. Section 8 describes relationships between max regret and the max generalised relative regret, firstly for small preferences spaces, and secondly when the denominator function is equal to 1. The latter leads to a way of computing the modified max regret using linear programming in Section 9. Section 10 concludes.

2 Background Model, Max Regret and Rescaling the Objectives

2.1 Reasoning based on Sets of Preference Models

We consider multi-objective decision making problems of the following form. We have a set A of alternatives, representing possible choices or decisions, where each alternative is scored according to each of p objectives (with higher scores being better). Thus, each alternative is associated with a (multi-objective utility) vector α in \mathbb{R}^p ; to simplify notation we identify the alternative with α . We would like to help a decision maker find their most preferred alternative(s).

We assume that the user preference model is one of a family parameterised by a set of scenarios \mathcal{W} ; associated with $w \in \mathcal{W}$ is a real-valued utility function f_w over the space \mathbb{R}^p of multi-objective vectors. In this paper we focus on the commonly used simple linear model of the user preferences based on (non-negative) weighted sums of objective values: for all $\alpha \in \mathbb{R}^p$, $f_w(\alpha) = w \cdot \alpha = \sum_{i=1}^p w(i)\alpha(i)$. Here, weights vector w is an element of \mathbb{R}_{\geq}^p , where \mathbb{R}_{\geq}^p is the set of vectors in \mathbb{R}^p , such that each co-ordinate is non-negative i.e., $w(i) \geq 0$ for all $i \in \{1, \dots, p\}$.

We have partial knowledge of the user preferences, expressed by a subset \mathcal{W} of all possible weights vectors \mathbb{R}_{\geq}^p . For a given weights vector w let $O_w(A)$ be the set of all elements α of A that are optimal in A with respect to w , i.e., such that $w \cdot \alpha \geq w \cdot \beta$ for all alternatives $\beta \in A$. We say that alternative $\alpha \in A$ is *necessarily optimal*, written $\alpha \in \text{NO}_{\mathcal{W}}(A)$, if α is optimal in A with respect to every weights vector in \mathcal{W} . If there exists a necessarily optimal alternative α then we can recommend it to the user, since it is optimal with respect to the user's (unknown) weights vector $w \in \mathcal{W}$. However, frequently, there will not be a necessarily optimal alternative; we could then recommend an alternative, for example, one minimising max regret; or we could elicit more information from the user.

A very natural form of user query is a comparison query between two alternatives α and β : asking which the user prefers. If the user states a preference for α over β , this corresponds with a constraint $w \cdot (\alpha - \beta) \geq 0$ that further restricts \mathcal{W} .

Preference Cone \mathcal{V}_Λ : For set $\Lambda \subseteq \mathbb{R}^p$ of utility vectors the preference cone $\mathcal{W}_\Lambda \subseteq \mathbb{R}_{\geq}^p$ is defined to be the set of weights vectors $w \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq}^p$ such that $0 \leq w \cdot \lambda$ ($= \sum_{i=1}^p w(i)\lambda(i)$) for all $\lambda \in \Lambda$. In particular, each λ may come from the answer to a comparison query, preferring an alternative α_λ over an alternative β_λ , implying $w \cdot (\alpha_\lambda - \beta_\lambda) \geq 0$, where $\alpha_\lambda - \beta_\lambda = \lambda$.

Cone and Conic Closure: More generally, a (linear) cone (in \mathbb{R}_{\geq}^p) \mathcal{V} is defined to be a subset of \mathbb{R}_{\geq}^p such that if $w \in \mathcal{V}$ then $rw \in \mathcal{V}$ for all real $r > 0$. Note that a cone need not be convex, although the cones we will be most interested in here will be convex, such as the preference cone \mathcal{V}_Λ . For any $\mathcal{W} \subseteq \mathbb{R}_{\geq}^p$, the conic closure $\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{W})$ is defined to be $\{rw : r > 0, w \in \mathcal{W}\}$; this is the unique smallest cone containing \mathcal{W} .

Notation \mathcal{V}^ψ , \mathcal{V}_Λ^ψ and \mathcal{V}_Λ^1 : For cone $\mathcal{V} \subseteq \mathbb{R}_{\geq}^p$ and $\psi \in \mathbb{R}^p$ we use the notation \mathcal{V}^ψ to mean $\{w \in \mathcal{V} : w \cdot \psi = 1\}$, which equals the intersection of \mathcal{V} with $(\mathbb{R}_{\geq}^p)^\psi$. For $\mathbf{1}$ being the p -dimensional vector of ones $(1, \dots, 1)$, \mathcal{V}^1 is the set of all elements w of \mathcal{V} whose components sum to 1. We use \mathcal{V}_Λ^ψ to mean $(\mathcal{V}_\Lambda)^\psi$; e.g., $\mathcal{V}_\Lambda^1 = (\mathcal{V}_\Lambda)^1$.

2.2 Max regret

The regret $R_A^w(\alpha)$ and the utility $Val_A(w)$: Let $w \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq}^p$, i.e., a vector with all components being non-negative. For finite set A of alternatives, the value (or utility) $Val_A(w)$ of A with respect to weights vector w is defined to be maximum utility over all elements of A , i.e., $\max_{\beta \in A} w \cdot \beta$. The regret $R_A^w(\alpha)$ for alternative α ($\in A$) in scenario w is defined by $R_A^w(\alpha) = Val_A(w) - w \cdot \alpha$; this is thus non-negative and measures how far α is from being optimal in A with respect to w . Hence, α is optimal with respect to user preference model w (i.e., $\alpha \in O_w(A)$) if and only if $R_A^w(\alpha) = 0$.

For our purposes it is convenient to define the max regret function based on a more general set of linear user models than is usual.

Max regret: For arbitrary $\mathcal{W} \subseteq \mathbb{R}_{\geq}^p$, and alternative α in set of alternatives A , define the max regret $MR_A(\alpha; \mathcal{W})$ of α to be equal to $\sup_{w \in \mathcal{W}} R_A^w(\alpha)$. It is thus in $[0, \infty]$, i.e., a non-negative real or equal to (positive) infinity. We have $MR_A(\alpha; \mathcal{W}) = 0$ if and only if for all $w \in \mathcal{W}$, $R_A^w(\alpha) = 0$ if and only if $\alpha \in \text{NO}_{\mathcal{W}}(A)$, i.e., α is optimal in A with respect to every user model in \mathcal{W} .

For any $\mathcal{W} \subseteq \mathbb{R}_{\geq}^p$ and real $r > 0$ we have $MR_A(\alpha; r\mathcal{W}) = r \times MR_A(\alpha; \mathcal{W})$. If \mathcal{V} is a cone then $r\mathcal{V} = \mathcal{V}$ and so $MR_A(\alpha; \mathcal{V}) = r \times MR_A(\alpha; \mathcal{V})$ for any $r > 0$, and hence, $MR_A(\alpha; \mathcal{V})$ is infinite for any α that is not necessarily optimal. To avoid such issues one restricts to bounded sets \mathcal{W} , and if one also assumes that \mathcal{W} is topologically closed, so that it is compact, then $MR_A(\alpha; \mathcal{W})$ is finite and equal to $\max_{w \in \mathcal{W}} R_A^w(\alpha)$.

In particular, for a cone $\mathcal{V} \subseteq \mathbb{R}_{\geq}^p$, such as a preference cone \mathcal{V}_Λ based on inputs Λ , one natural approach is to only consider weights vectors that are normalised in a particular sense; one might use $\mathcal{W} = \mathcal{V}^1 = \{w \in \mathcal{V} : w \cdot \mathbf{1} = \sum_{i=1}^p w(i) = 1\}$. More generally one might normalise with a weighted sum: for strictly positive vector $\sigma \in \mathbb{R}^p$ we can use $\mathcal{W} = \mathcal{V}^\sigma = \{w \in \mathcal{V} : w \cdot \sigma = 1\}$.

Preference-vacuous: Alternative ways of bounding a cone \mathcal{V} are also possible, such as only considering the elements all of whose components are in $[0, 1]$. More generally we can intersect \mathcal{V} with some compact set $\mathcal{U} \subseteq \mathbb{R}_{\geq}^p$. For our purposes, the key property of \mathcal{U} is that it is non-informative regarding comparison queries: consider $\gamma_1, \gamma_2 \in \mathbb{R}^p$ such that neither Pareto-dominates the other; then learning the fact that $w \in \mathcal{U}$ should not tell us whether $w \cdot \gamma_1 \geq w \cdot \gamma_2$ holds. In fact, it is sufficient to assume that \mathcal{U} is what we call

preference-vacuous: that its conic closure $\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{U})$ is the whole of \mathbb{R}_{\geq}^p , i.e., if for all $w \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq}^p$ there exists $r > 0$ such that $rw \in \mathcal{U}$. If $\mathcal{V} \subseteq \mathbb{R}_{\geq}^p$ is a cone and \mathcal{U} is preference-vacuous then $\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{V} \cap \mathcal{U}) = \mathcal{V}$.

Lemma 1. *If $\mathcal{V} \subseteq \mathbb{R}_{\geq}^p$ is a cone and \mathcal{U} is preference-vacuous then $\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{V} \cap \mathcal{U}) = \mathcal{V}$.*

Proof: By monotonicity of the conic closure operator we have $\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{V} \cap \mathcal{U}) \subseteq \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{V})$, which equals \mathcal{V} since \mathcal{V} is a cone. Conversely, consider any $w \in \mathcal{V}$. Since \mathcal{U} is preference-vacuous there exists $r > 0$ such that $rw \in \mathcal{U}$, and so $rw \in \mathcal{V} \cap \mathcal{U}$ which implies that $w \in \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{V} \cap \mathcal{U})$, thus proving $\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{V} \cap \mathcal{U}) \supseteq \mathcal{V}$. \square

A fundamental property of max regret is that it is translation-invariant, i.e., if one adds a vector $\delta \in \mathbb{R}^p$ to each element of A then this does not change the max regret: $MR_{A+\delta}(\alpha + \delta; \mathcal{W}) = MR_A(\alpha; \mathcal{W})$, where $A + \delta$ is defined to be $\{\gamma + \delta : \gamma \in A\}$.

2.3 Rescaling and its effect on max regret

Rescaling the objectives, i.e., changing their units, involves multiplying the objective values by positive reals. This can be expressed using pointwise product of vectors. For $\alpha, \beta \in \mathbb{R}^p$, their pointwise product $\alpha \odot \beta \in \mathbb{R}^p$ is defined by $(\alpha \odot \beta)(i) = \alpha(i)\beta(i)$ for $i \in \{1, \dots, p\}$. Pointwise product is commutative and associative, and, in a certain sense, commutes with dot product: for $\alpha, \beta, \gamma \in \mathbb{R}^p$, $(\alpha \odot \beta) \cdot \gamma = \alpha \cdot (\beta \odot \gamma) = \sum_{i=1}^p \alpha(i)\beta(i)\gamma(i)$. In the obvious way we extend to sets: if $\alpha \in \mathbb{R}^p$ and $B \subseteq \mathbb{R}^p$ we define $\alpha \odot B = B \odot \alpha = \{\alpha \odot \beta : \beta \in B\}$.

A rescaling vector τ has every co-ordinate strictly greater than zero, so is an element of $\mathbb{R}_{+}^p = \{\tau \in \mathbb{R}^p : \forall i \in \{1, \dots, p\}, \tau(i) > 0\}$. For $\tau \in \mathbb{R}_{+}^p$, we define $\tau^{-1} \in \mathbb{R}_{+}^p$ by $\tau^{-1}(i) = 1/\tau(i)$ for each $i \in \{1, \dots, p\}$. Thus, $\tau \odot \tau^{-1} = \mathbf{1}$.

Rescaling the objectives involves a transformation of (representations of) alternatives, $\gamma \rightarrow \gamma \odot \tau$, where $\tau \in \mathbb{R}_{+}^p$. Here, one unit of objective i in the original scale is equivalent to $\tau(i)$ units of the new scale for objective i . This transformation affects elements of A (representing the alternatives), as well as the preference inputs $\lambda \in \Lambda$ (because if $\lambda = \alpha_\lambda - \beta_\lambda$ then $\lambda \odot \tau = \alpha_\lambda \odot \tau - \beta_\lambda \odot \tau$). Regarding preference cones, it is easily seen that $\mathcal{V}_{\Lambda \odot \tau} = \mathcal{V}_\Lambda \odot \tau^{-1}$. For any alternative $\gamma \in A$, γ is changed to $\gamma \odot \tau$, and if $w \in \mathcal{V}_\Lambda$ is mapped to $w \odot \tau^{-1}$ then the dot product $w \cdot \gamma$ will be unchanged by the rescaling, since $(w \odot \tau^{-1}) \cdot (\gamma \odot \tau) = w \cdot (\gamma \odot \tau \odot \tau^{-1}) = w \cdot \gamma$. Because max regret is composed of such dot products, one might imagine that rescaling would not change max regret; however, this is not correct since it does not take into account the normalisation (or, more generally, a bounding) of the preference cone required for max regret: if $w \in \mathcal{W}_\Lambda^1$ then $w \odot \tau^{-1}$ will not be normalised in the same way; thus, w is mapped instead to $v = \frac{w \odot \tau^{-1}}{w \cdot \tau^{-1}}$, in order that v satisfies the normalisation condition $v \cdot \mathbf{1} = 1$.

We consider an example from [23] which illustrates that changing the units can considerably alter the values of max regret, and can lead to a different alternative minimising max regret.

Example 1. *We have $p = 2$ objectives, with the second objective representing value in euros, and a single elicited preference that alternative $\alpha = (20, 2)$ is at least as good as alternative $\gamma = (24, 1)$, leading to $\Lambda = \{\lambda\}$ where $\lambda = \alpha - \gamma = (-4, 1)$, and \mathcal{V}_Λ being the set of all $w \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq}^2$ with $w \cdot \lambda \geq 0$. The set \mathcal{V}_Λ^1 of feasible normalised preference models is then all pairs w such that $w(1) + w(2) = 1$ and $w(2) \geq 4w(1) \geq 0$; this is a line with endpoints $u = (0, 1)$ and $v = (\frac{1}{5}, \frac{4}{5})$. We consider the set of alternatives $A = \{\alpha, \beta\}$, where*

$\beta = (44, 1)$. *The max regret of α is equal to $(\beta - \alpha) \cdot v = 4$, and the max regret of β equals $(\alpha - \beta) \cdot u = 1$.*

However, if we instead express the financial gain in cents rather than euros then the new representations of the two alternatives are $\alpha' = (20, 200)$ and $\beta' = (44, 100)$ with the new preference vector $\lambda' = \alpha' - \beta' = (-24, 100)$. The max regret for α' is around 19, and the max regret of β' is equal to 100, so the first alternative now looks much more promising than the second.

In fact, as shown in Example 4 of [23], with more extreme scaling, the ratio of the max regret of β and that of α can be made arbitrarily large. Proposition 1, which is a more general form of the first part of Theorem 1 of [23], shows that changing the scales is equivalent to applying max regret with a different way of bounding/normalising the preference cone.

We first give a technical lemma regarding the effects of applying a rescaling vector τ .

Lemma 2. *Consider any $\tau \in \mathbb{R}_{+}^p$.*

- (i) *For $\Lambda \subseteq \mathbb{R}^p$, $\mathcal{V}_{\Lambda \odot \tau}$ is equal to $\mathcal{V}_\Lambda \odot \tau^{-1}$.*
- (ii) *For $\mathcal{W}, \mathcal{U} \subseteq \mathbb{R}_{\geq}^p$, $(\mathcal{W} \odot \tau^{-1}) \cap \mathcal{U} = (\mathcal{W} \cap (\mathcal{U} \odot \tau)) \odot \tau^{-1}$.*
- (iii) *For $w \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq}^p$, finite $A \subseteq \mathbb{R}^p$ and $\alpha \in A$, $R_{A \odot \tau}^{w \odot \tau^{-1}}(\alpha \odot \tau) = R_A^w(\alpha)$.*

Proof: (i): $w \in \mathcal{V}_{\Lambda \odot \tau}$ if and only if for all $\lambda \in \Lambda$ we have $w \cdot (\lambda \odot \tau) \geq 0$, i.e., for all $\lambda \in \Lambda$ we have $(w \odot \tau) \cdot \lambda \geq 0$, i.e., $w \odot \tau \in \mathcal{V}_\Lambda$, which holds if and only if $w \in \mathcal{V}_\Lambda \odot \tau^{-1}$.

(ii): $w \in (\mathcal{W} \cap (\mathcal{U} \odot \tau)) \odot \tau^{-1}$ if and only if $w \odot \tau \in \mathcal{W} \cap (\mathcal{U} \odot \tau)$ if and only if $w \odot \tau \in \mathcal{W}$ and $w \odot \tau \in (\mathcal{U} \odot \tau) \odot \tau^{-1} = \mathcal{U}$, which is if and only if $w \in (\mathcal{W} \odot \tau^{-1}) \cap \mathcal{U}$.

(iii): $R_{A \odot \tau}^{w \odot \tau^{-1}}(\alpha \odot \tau) = \max_{\gamma \odot \tau \in A \odot \tau} (w \odot \tau^{-1}) \cdot (\gamma \odot \tau) - (w \odot \tau^{-1}) \cdot (\alpha \odot \tau) = \max_{\gamma \in A} w \cdot \gamma - w \cdot \alpha = R_A^w(\alpha)$. \square

Proposition 1. *For $\Lambda \subseteq \mathbb{R}^p$ and $\tau \in \mathbb{R}_{+}^p$, finite $A \subseteq \mathbb{R}^p$ and $\alpha \in A$, $MR_{A \odot \tau}(\alpha \odot \tau; \mathcal{V}_{\Lambda \odot \tau}^1) = MR_A(\alpha; \mathcal{V}_\Lambda^1)$, where $\sigma = \tau^{-1}$.*

More generally, for $\mathcal{U} \subseteq \mathbb{R}_{\geq}^p$ (in particular for preference-vacuous \mathcal{U}) we have $MR_{A \odot \tau}(\alpha \odot \tau; \mathcal{V}_{\Lambda \odot \tau} \cap \mathcal{U}) = MR_A(\alpha; \mathcal{V}_\Lambda \cap (\mathcal{U} \odot \tau))$.

Proof: Using Lemma 2(i) and (ii), $\mathcal{V}_{\Lambda \odot \tau} \cap \mathcal{U} = (\mathcal{V}_\Lambda \odot \tau^{-1}) \cap \mathcal{U} = (\mathcal{V}_\Lambda \cap (\mathcal{U} \odot \tau)) \odot \tau^{-1}$, and so, $MR_{A \odot \tau}(\alpha \odot \tau; \mathcal{V}_{\Lambda \odot \tau} \cap \mathcal{U})$ equals $MR_{A \odot \tau}(\alpha \odot \tau; (\mathcal{V}_\Lambda \cap (\mathcal{U} \odot \tau)) \odot \tau^{-1})$. The latter equals the supremum, over w in $\mathcal{V}_\Lambda \cap (\mathcal{U} \odot \tau)$, of $R_{A \odot \tau}^{w \odot \tau^{-1}}(\alpha \odot \tau)$, which, using Lemma 2(iii), equals $MR_A(\alpha; \mathcal{V}_\Lambda \cap (\mathcal{U} \odot \tau))$. \square

2.4 Max relative regret:

A variation of max regret is max relative regret [11, 1] which can be written in our (maximising utility) setting as $\sup_{w \in \mathcal{W}} \frac{Val_A(w) - w \cdot \alpha}{Val_A(w)}$. It can be seen that this is scale-invariant (using the same reasoning as used for Theorem 14 in Section 6 below). However, it loses the translation-invariance property, because the denominator $Val_A(w)$ is changed by translation, but the numerator is unchanged, so the ratio is changed. In fact, the ordering of the max relative regret of alternatives can even be changed by translation, as shown by the following example.

Example 2. *Like in Example 1, let $\alpha = (20, 2)$ and $\beta = (44, 1)$; and let $\delta = (N, 0)$ for some non-negative N . We consider $A + \delta =$*

$\{\alpha + \delta, \beta + \delta\}$, and let $\mathcal{W} = \{w_r : r \in [0, 1]\}$, where $w_r = (r, 1 - r)$. Now, $w_r \cdot (\alpha + \delta) \geq w_r \cdot (\beta + \delta)$ if and only if $w_r \cdot (\alpha - \beta) \geq 0$ iff $(r, 1 - r) \cdot (-24, 1) = 1 - 25r \geq 0$, i.e., $r \leq \frac{1}{25}$. The max relative regret of $\beta + \delta$ is then given by setting $r = 0$, and is equal to $\frac{1}{2}$ because $\text{Val}_{A+\delta}(w_0) = w_0 \cdot (\alpha + \delta) = 2$.

For $r \geq 1/25$, $\text{Val}_{A+\delta}(w) = w \cdot (\beta + \delta) = 1 + (N + 43)r$. The relative regret for α with respect to w_r is $\frac{25r-1}{1+(N+43)r}$.

If we set $N = 0$ and so $\delta = (0, 0)$ then we obtain that the max relative regret of α is at least $\frac{w_1 \cdot (\beta - \alpha)}{w_1 \cdot \beta} = \frac{24}{44} > 0.5$, and so greater than the max relative regret of β . If however we set any N with $N > 7$ then for all $r > 0$ we have $\frac{w_r \cdot (\beta - \alpha)}{w_r \cdot \beta} < \frac{25r}{(N+43)r} < 0.5$, so the max relative regret of $\alpha + \delta$ is less than that of $\beta + \delta$.

3 Max D -Relative Regret and Some Basic Properties

In this section we define max D -relative regret, for (families of) functions D , where the regret of an alternative α is divided by a term $D_A(w)$ that depends on the set A of alternatives, but not on α in particular. We show that max D -relative regret maintains key properties of max regret, but, unlike max regret, it can be defined on a preference cone \mathcal{V}_Λ , without needing normalisation or bounding (because of the positive homogeneity condition).

Definition of set \mathcal{D} of denominator families: We consider families D , of non-negative real-valued functions D_A on \mathbb{R}_+^p for all finite $A \subseteq \mathbb{R}^p$, satisfying the positive homogeneity condition $D_A(rw) = rD_A(w)$ for all real $r > 0$ and all $w \in \mathbb{R}_+^p$. Let \mathcal{D} be the set of all such families.

A simple instance of such a family $D \in \mathcal{D}$ is given by $D_A(w) = w \cdot \sigma$ for some strictly positive vector $\sigma \in \mathbb{R}_+^p$; e.g., one might use $\sigma = \mathbf{1} = (1, \dots, 1)$.

Let $\alpha \in A$ and $w \in \mathbb{R}_+^p$; recall that $R_A^w(\alpha) = \text{Val}_A(w) - w \cdot \alpha = \max_{\beta \in A} w \cdot \beta - w \cdot \alpha$. Define the D -relative regret

$$RR_A^D(\alpha; w) = \begin{cases} R_A^w(\alpha)/D_A(w) & \text{if } D_A(w) > 0; \\ 0 & \text{if } R_A^w(\alpha) = D_A(w) = 0; \\ \infty & \text{if } R_A^w(\alpha) > 0 \text{ and } D_A(w) = 0. \end{cases}$$

We define, for $\mathcal{W} \subseteq \mathbb{R}_+^p$, the max D -relative regret

$$MRR_A^D(\alpha; \mathcal{W}) = \sup_{w \in \mathcal{W}} RR_A^D(\alpha; w).$$

So, the max D -relative regret is the supremum, over weights vectors $w \in \mathcal{W}$, of the ratio between the regret $R_A^w(\alpha)$ and the value of the denominator function $D_A(w)$. It takes values in $[0, \infty]$. For example, with a cone $\mathcal{V} \subseteq \mathbb{R}_+^p$, and with $\mathcal{W} = \mathcal{V}^1$ being all elements of \mathcal{V} whose components sum to 1, and with $D_A(w) = w \cdot \mathbf{1} = \sum_{i=1}^p w(i)$, max D -relative regret is just equal to max regret on \mathcal{W} , and we have $MR_A(\alpha; \mathcal{V}^1) = MRR_A^D(\alpha; \mathcal{V}^1) = MRR_A^D(\alpha; \mathcal{V})$. We give more interesting examples of such functions $D \in \mathcal{D}$ in Section 4.

We have the basic property below, that the max D -relative regret of α is non-negative, equalling zero if and only if α is necessarily optimal.

Proposition 2. Consider¹ $D \in \mathcal{D}$, finite $A \subseteq \mathbb{R}^p$, and $\alpha \in A$ and

¹ Most of the formal results in the paper consider a function $MRR_A^D(\alpha; \mathcal{W})$. To avoid unnecessary repetition, unless otherwise specified, it should be assumed that (the denominator function) D is an arbitrary element of \mathcal{D} , (the set of alternatives) A is an arbitrary finite subset of \mathbb{R}^p , (alternative) α is an arbitrary element of A , and (set of weights vectors) \mathcal{W} is an arbitrary subset of \mathbb{R}_+^p (the set of all vectors in \mathbb{R}^p for which each component is non-negative).

let $\mathcal{W} \subseteq \mathbb{R}_+^p$. Then $MRR_A^D(\alpha; \mathcal{W}) \geq 0$. It equals zero if and only if $\alpha \in \text{NO}_{\mathcal{W}}(A)$.

Proof: Since $\alpha \in A$ we have $R_A^w(\alpha) \geq 0$, and thus, $RR_A^D(\alpha; w) \geq 0$ for all $w \in \mathcal{W}$, because $D_A(w) \geq 0$ for all $w \in \mathbb{R}_+^p$. Hence, $MRR_A^D(\alpha; \mathcal{W}) \geq 0$.

For $w \in \mathbb{R}_+^p$ we have $RR_A^D(\alpha; w) = 0$ if and only if $R_A^w(\alpha) = 0$, which is if and only if $\alpha \in O_w(A)$. Hence, $MRR_A^D(\alpha; \mathcal{W}) = 0$ if and only if for all $w \in \mathcal{W}$ we have $\alpha \in O_w(A)$, i.e., $\alpha \in \text{NO}_{\mathcal{W}}(A)$. \square

Recall that $\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{W})$ is the conic closure of \mathcal{W} , i.e., the smallest cone containing \mathcal{W} . For any $w \in \mathbb{R}_+^p$ and $r > 0$, $R_A^{rw}(\alpha) = rR_A^w(\alpha)$ and $D_A(rw) = rD_A(w)$, and so $RR_A^D(\alpha; rw) = RR_A^D(\alpha; w)$. This leads to the following result, which also implies that if two sets $\mathcal{W}, \mathcal{W}'$ have the same conic closure then $MRR_A^D(\alpha; \mathcal{W}) = MRR_A^D(\alpha; \mathcal{W}')$.

Theorem 3 (Conic Closure). $MRR_A^D(\alpha; \mathcal{W}) = MRR_A^D(\alpha; \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{W}))$.

Proof: Let $R_1 = \{RR_A^D(\alpha; w) : w \in \mathcal{W}\}$ and let $R_2 = \{RR_A^D(\alpha; w) : w \in \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{W})\}$. Because $MRR_A^D(\alpha; \mathcal{W}) = \sup R_1$ and $MRR_A^D(\alpha; \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{W})) = \sup R_2$, it is sufficient to show that $R_1 = R_2$.

Since $\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{W}) \supseteq \mathcal{W}$ we have $R_1 \subseteq R_2$. Conversely, consider any $x \in R_2$, so that there exists $w \in \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{W})$ with $x = RR_A^D(\alpha; w)$. There exists $r > 0$ with $rw \in \mathcal{W}$. Then, $R_A^{rw}(\alpha) = rR_A^w(\alpha)$ and $D_A(rw) = rD_A(w)$ and so $R_1 \ni RR_A^D(\alpha; rw) = RR_A^D(\alpha; w) = x$, which shows that $x \in R_1$, completing the proof that $R_1 = R_2$. \square

Theorem 3 means that we can directly use a preference cone of the form \mathcal{V}_Λ , and that it is equivalent to considering normalised or bounded versions of it. In particular, for any $\sigma \in \mathbb{R}_+^p$, $MRR_A^D(\alpha; \mathcal{V}_\Lambda^\sigma) = MRR_A^D(\alpha; \mathcal{V}_\Lambda)$.

Monotonicity with respect to \mathcal{W} follows immediately from the definition. This means that learning more information about the user model (and so decreasing \mathcal{W}) can never increase the value of max D -relative regret.

Proposition 4. If $\mathcal{W}' \subseteq \mathcal{W}$ then $MRR_A^D(\alpha; \mathcal{W}') \leq MRR_A^D(\alpha; \mathcal{W})$.

The following decomposition property will be important for computation (see Sections 7 and 9): breaking up \mathcal{W} into parts that enable simple computation.

Proposition 5 (Decomposition). If $\mathcal{W} = \bigcup_{j=1}^J \mathcal{W}_j$ then $MRR_A^D(\alpha; \mathcal{W}) = \max_{j=1}^J MRR_A^D(\alpha; \mathcal{W}_j)$.

Proof: Proposition 4 implies that $MRR_A^D(\alpha; \mathcal{W}) \geq \max_{j=1}^J MRR_A^D(\alpha; \mathcal{W}_j)$. For the converse, let $t = MRR_A^D(\alpha; \mathcal{W})$. Then there exists a sequence w_1, w_2, \dots with each $w_k \in \mathcal{W}$ with $RR_A^D(\alpha; w_k)$ a non-decreasing sequence in k , and with $\lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} RR_A^D(\alpha; w_k) = t$. There exists $j \in \{1, \dots, J\}$ such that \mathcal{W}_j contains w_k for infinitely many indices k . Write this subsequence as v_1, v_2, \dots . Then $\lim_{m \rightarrow \infty} RR_A^D(\alpha; v_m) = t$, and so $MRR_A^D(\alpha; \mathcal{W}_j) \geq t$, showing that $MRR_A^D(\alpha; \mathcal{W}) \leq \max_{j=1}^J MRR_A^D(\alpha; \mathcal{W}_j)$. \square

The next simple technical result is useful for some proofs.

Lemma 3. Define, for $t \geq 0$, and $w \in \mathbb{R}_+^p$, $g_t(w) = R_A^w(\alpha) - tD_A(w)$. For arbitrary set $\mathcal{W} \subseteq \mathbb{R}_+^p$, and $t \geq 0$ we have $MRR_A^D(\alpha; \mathcal{W}) \leq t$ if and only if $\sup_{w \in \mathcal{W}} g_t(w) \leq 0$.

Proof: We have $MRR_A^D(\alpha; \mathcal{W}) \leq t$ if and only if for all $w \in \mathcal{W}$, $RR_A^D(\alpha; w) \leq t$. Now, $RR_A^D(\alpha; w) \leq t \iff R_A^w(\alpha) \leq tD_A(w) \iff g_t(w) \leq 0$. Hence, $MRR_A^D(\alpha; \mathcal{W}) \leq t$ if and only if for all $w \in \mathcal{W}$, $g_t(w) \leq 0$, which is if and only if $\sup_{w \in \mathcal{W}} g_t(w) \leq 0$. \square

Often the supremum in the definition of max D -relative regret can be replaced by a maximum. The following result gives two instances of this. (Some other instances are given in Corollary 18 below in Section 7.)

Proposition 6. *Given $D \in \mathcal{D}$ and finite $A \subseteq \mathbb{R}^p$, suppose that the function D_A is continuous. Let \mathcal{W}' be the topological closure of \mathcal{W} . We have $MRR_A^D(\alpha; \mathcal{W}) = MRR_A^D(\alpha; \mathcal{W}')$.*

If D_A is non-zero on \mathcal{W} and either \mathcal{W} is compact or a topologically closed cone then $MRR_A^D(\alpha; \mathcal{W}) = \max_{w \in \mathcal{W}} RR_A^D(\alpha; w)$.

Proof: For $\alpha \in A$, $R_A^w(\alpha)$ is a continuous function of w , and thus, for any $t \in \mathbb{R}$, $g_t(w) = R_A^w(\alpha) - tD_A(w)$ is a continuous function of w . Suppose that w_1, w_2, \dots is a sequence of elements of \mathcal{W} converging to some $w \in \mathbb{R}^p$. By continuity of g_t , we have $g_t(w) = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} g_t(w_n)$. Thus, if $g_t(w_n) \leq 0$ for all n then $g_t(w) \leq 0$.

Now, we have $MRR_A^D(\alpha; \mathcal{W}) \leq t$ if and only if for all $w \in \mathcal{W}$, $RR_A^D(\alpha; w) \leq t$, which, using Lemma 3, is if and only if for all $w \in \mathcal{W}$, $g_t(w) \leq 0$; by the argument in the first paragraph, this is equivalent to for all $w \in \mathcal{W}'$, $g_t(w) \leq 0$, i.e., $MRR_A^D(\alpha; \mathcal{W}') \leq t$. This proves that $MRR_A^D(\alpha; \mathcal{W}) = MRR_A^D(\alpha; \mathcal{W}')$.

Assume now that D_A is non-zero on \mathcal{W} . If \mathcal{W} is compact then, because $RR_A^D(\alpha; w)$ is a continuous function on \mathcal{W} , the image of \mathcal{W} in \mathbb{R} is compact. This implies that the bounds of $RR_A^D(\alpha; w)$ over $w \in \mathcal{W}$ are attained, so there exists $w' \in \mathcal{W}$ such that $RR_A^D(\alpha; w') = \sup_{w \in \mathcal{W}} RR_A^D(\alpha; w)$, and hence, $MRR_A^D(\alpha; \mathcal{W}) = \max_{w \in \mathcal{W}} RR_A^D(\alpha; w)$.

If, on the other hand, \mathcal{W} is a closed cone then \mathcal{W}^1 is compact, being the intersection of the closed set \mathcal{W} and a compact set. $RR_A^D(\alpha; w)$ is a continuous function on \mathcal{W}^1 , and so the image of \mathcal{W}^1 in \mathbb{R} is compact. As in the last paragraph, the supremum over \mathcal{W}^1 is attained, so there exists $w' \in \mathcal{W}^1 \subseteq \mathcal{W}$ such that $RR_A^D(\alpha; w') = \sup_{w \in \mathcal{W}^1} RR_A^D(\alpha; w) = MRR_A^D(\alpha; \mathcal{W}^1)$, which equals $MRR_A^D(\alpha; \mathcal{W})$ by Theorem 3, since $\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{W}^1) = \mathcal{W}$. This proves that $MRR_A^D(\alpha; \mathcal{W}) = \max_{w \in \mathcal{W}} RR_A^D(\alpha; w)$. \square

4 Four Choices of Function D

We give four particular choices of function D that all relate to a range of values of utility within A , and which, as we show in later sections, lead to good invariance and computational properties of max D -relative regret.

Given finite $A \subseteq \mathbb{R}^p$, we define the pointwise max, $\bar{A} \in \mathbb{R}^p$, by, for each $i \in \{1, \dots, p\}$, $\bar{A}(i) = \max_{\alpha \in A} \alpha(i)$; the pointwise min, $\underline{A} \in \mathbb{R}^p$, by $\underline{A}(i) = \min_{\alpha \in A} \alpha(i)$; and the mean, $\hat{A} \in \mathbb{R}^p$, to be $\frac{1}{|A|} \sum_{\alpha \in A} \alpha$. Recall $Val_A(w) = \max_{\alpha \in A} w \cdot \alpha$; similarly we define $Wor_A(w) = \min_{\alpha \in A} w \cdot \alpha$, which is the worst utility (with respect to w) of any element of A . The definitions easily lead to the following inequalities.

Proposition 7. *For all $w \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq}^p$ we have $w \cdot \bar{A} \geq Val_A(w) \geq w \cdot \hat{A} \geq Wor_A(w) \geq w \cdot \underline{A}$.*

Proof: Consider any $w \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq}^p$. We have $w \cdot \hat{A} = \frac{1}{|A|} \sum_{\alpha \in A} w \cdot \alpha$. Hence, $Val_A(w) = \max_{\alpha \in A} w \cdot \alpha \geq w \cdot \hat{A} \geq \min_{\alpha \in A} w \cdot \alpha = Wor_A(w)$.

There exists $\beta, \gamma \in A$ such that $w \cdot \beta = Val_A(w) = \max_{\alpha \in A} w \cdot \alpha$, and $w \cdot \gamma = Wor_A(w) = \min_{\alpha \in A} w \cdot \alpha$. We have, for all $i \in \{1, \dots, p\}$, $\bar{A}(i) \geq \beta(i)$ and $\gamma(i) \geq \underline{A}(i)$, so, since $w(i) \geq 0$, $w(i)\bar{A}(i) \geq w(i)\beta(i)$ and $w(i)\gamma(i) \geq w(i)\underline{A}(i)$. Summing over all $i \in \{1, \dots, p\}$ gives $w \cdot \bar{A} \geq Val_A(w)$ and $Wor_A(w) \geq w \cdot \underline{A}$. \square

We will analyse in detail the following four particular elements of \mathcal{D} . Let us define, for finite $A \subseteq \mathbb{R}^p$ and $w \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq}^p$:

$$\begin{aligned} D_A^0(w) &= Val_A(w) - w \cdot \hat{A}. \\ D_A^1(w) &= Val_A(w) - Wor_A(w). \\ D_A^2(w) &= Val_A(w) - w \cdot \underline{A}. \\ D_A^3(w) &= w \cdot (\bar{A} - \underline{A}). \end{aligned}$$

All these definitions are based on a range of preference values. $D_A^1(w)$ is arguably the most intuitive, as it gives the difference between the maximum and minimum utility obtained by elements of A . $D_A^1(w)$ can be written as $\max_{\gamma \in A} R_A^w(\gamma)$, so $RR_A^{D^1}(\alpha; w) = \frac{R_A^w(\alpha)}{\max_{\gamma \in A} R_A^w(\gamma)}$, the ratio of the regret of α with the worst regret of any alternative in A . However, we shall see in Sections 7 and 9 that it seems to be computationally more costly than the other three.

D^2 can be considered as a version of D^1 , where we approximate $Wor_A(w)$ by $w \cdot \underline{A}$. D^0 is somewhat similar, but with smaller values; it has the advantage that it is less affected by a very poor element of A . D^3 can also be viewed as an approximation of D^1 ; using D^3 , max D -relative regret corresponds exactly with max regret if one first rescales A to have unit ranges for each objective (see Proposition 15 below).

The orderings expressed in Proposition 7 lead to inequalities between the families D^k .

Proposition 8. *Consider any $w \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq}^p$ and any $k \in \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$. For any $r > 0$, $D_A^k(rw) = rD_A^k(w)$. We have $0 \leq D_A^0(w) \leq D_A^1(w) \leq D_A^2(w) \leq D_A^3(w)$; hence, $D^k \in \mathcal{D}$. Also, for any $\alpha \in A$, $R_A^w(\alpha) \leq D_A^1(w)$; and if $D_A^k(w) = 0$ then $R_A^w(\alpha) = 0$.*

Proof: For $r > 0$ and each $\gamma \in \mathbb{R}^p$ we have $(rw) \cdot \gamma = r(w \cdot \gamma)$, which implies that $Val_A(rw) = rVal_A(w)$ and $Wor_A(rw) = rWor_A(w)$; these imply $D_A^k(rw) = rD_A^k(w)$ for each $k \in \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$.

For all $w \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq}^p$, the orderings $0 \leq D_A^0(w) \leq D_A^1(w) \leq D_A^2(w) \leq D_A^3(w)$ follow immediately from Proposition 7. This implies, for arbitrary $k \in \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$, that $D_A^k(w) \geq 0$ for all $w \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq}^p$ and all finite $A \subseteq \mathbb{R}^p$; hence, $D^k \in \mathcal{D}$.

We also have, for all $w \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq}^p$, $w \cdot \alpha \geq Wor_A$, and so $R_A^w(\alpha) = Val_A(w) - w \cdot \alpha \leq Val_A(w) - Wor_A = D_A^1(w)$, and so $R_A^w(\alpha) \leq D_A^1(w)$.

Now suppose that $D_A^k(w) = 0$ for some $k \in \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$. By an earlier part, $D_A^0(w) = 0$, i.e., $Val_A(w) = w \cdot \hat{A}$, so that $\max_{\beta \in A} w \cdot \beta = \frac{1}{|A|} \sum_{\gamma \in A} w \cdot \gamma$. If the maximum of a finite set of numbers is equal to the mean, then they are all equal, and so, for all $\gamma \in A$ we have $w \cdot \gamma = Val_A(w)$, in particular, $w \cdot \alpha = Val_A(w)$, and thus, $R_A^w(\alpha) = 0$. \square

The orderings from Proposition 8 lead to (reversed) orderings for max D -relative regret. In particular, this implies that $MRR_A^{D^1}(\alpha; \mathcal{W})$ is in the interval $[MRR_A^{D^2}(\alpha; \mathcal{W}), MRR_A^{D^0}(\alpha; \mathcal{W})]$. These bounds could be helpful in computing the minimax D^1 -relative regret, which seems to be computationally harder than for D^0 or D^2 (see Sections 7 and 9 below).

Theorem 9. $MRR_A^{D^0}(\alpha; \mathcal{W}) \geq MRR_A^{D^1}(\alpha; \mathcal{W}) \geq MRR_A^{D^2}(\alpha; \mathcal{W}) \geq MRR_A^{D^3}(\alpha; \mathcal{W})$. In addition, for all $k \in \{1, 2, 3\}$, $MRR_A^{D^k}(\alpha; \mathcal{W}) \leq 1$.

Proof: By Proposition 8 we have that $D^k \in \mathcal{D}$ for all $k \in \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$. Also, for all $w \in \mathbb{R}_+^p$, the orderings $0 \leq D_A^0(w) \leq D_A^1(w) \leq D_A^2(w) \leq D_A^3(w)$. This implies $RR_A^{D^0}(\alpha; w) \geq RR_A^{D^1}(\alpha; w) \geq RR_A^{D^2}(\alpha; w) \geq RR_A^{D^3}(\alpha; w)$, and thus, $MRR_A^{D^0}(\alpha; \mathcal{W}) \geq MRR_A^{D^1}(\alpha; \mathcal{W}) \geq MRR_A^{D^2}(\alpha; \mathcal{W}) \geq MRR_A^{D^3}(\alpha; \mathcal{W})$. In addition, by Proposition 8 we have $R_A^w(\alpha) \leq D_A^1(w)$, which implies $RR_A^{D^1}(\alpha; w) \leq 1$, and hence, $MRR_A^{D^1}(\alpha; \mathcal{W}) \leq 1$, which, by the first part, implies $MRR_A^{D^k}(\alpha; \mathcal{W}) \leq 1$ for $k \in \{2, 3\}$. \square

If α is ever (i.e., w.r.t. some $w \in \mathcal{W}$) the worst element in A then we will have $MRR_A^{D^1}(\alpha; \mathcal{W}) = 1$, which means that there always exists at least one alternative with the maximum possible D^1 -relative regret value of 1. In particular, for the very special case when there are only two alternatives in A , then for both $\alpha \in A$ we have $MRR_A^{D^1}(\alpha; \mathcal{W}) = 1$ unless α is necessarily optimal. Also in this case of $|A| = 2$ we will have $MRR_A^{D^0}(\alpha; \mathcal{W}) = 2$ unless α is necessarily optimal.

This is because $w \cdot \hat{A}$ will then be equal to $\frac{1}{2}(Val_A(w) + Wor_A(w))$, and so $D_A^0(w) = Val_A(w) - w \cdot \hat{A} = \frac{1}{2}(Val_A(w) - Wor_A(w)) = \frac{1}{2}D_A^1(w)$.

Thus, with Example 1 involving two alternatives, max D^k -relative regret is not so interesting for $k = 0, 1$. But we have $MRR_A^{D^2}(\alpha; \mathcal{V}_\Lambda^1) = 5/6$ and $MRR_A^{D^2}(\beta; \mathcal{V}_\Lambda^1) = 1$. And, $MRR_A^{D^3}(\alpha; \mathcal{V}_\Lambda^1) = 5/7$ and $MRR_A^{D^3}(\beta; \mathcal{V}_\Lambda^1) = 1$. By Theorem 3 (conic closure), we have e.g., $MRR_A^{D^2}(\alpha; \mathcal{V}_\Lambda^1) = MRR_A^{D^2}(\alpha; \mathcal{V}_\Lambda) = MRR_A^{D^2}(\alpha; \mathcal{V}_\Lambda^\sigma)$ for any $\sigma \in \mathbb{R}_+^p$, and so the particular normalisation used makes no difference for max D^k -relative regret. Proposition 1 relates a change of scales to a change in normalisation, so it is not surprising then that changing the units makes no difference in Example 1: $MRR_{A'}^{D^2}(\alpha'; \mathcal{V}_{\Lambda'}^1) = MRR_A^{D^2}(\alpha; \mathcal{V}_\Lambda^1)$. We prove a general result about scale-invariance in Section 6.

The following example illustrates the differences in max D^k -relative regret for the four values of k .

In this example, $\underline{A} = (0, 0)$, so the max relative regret of an alternative θ is equal to $MRR_A^{D^2}(\theta; \mathcal{V}_\Lambda^1)$.

Example 3. Let $A = \{\alpha, \beta, \gamma\}$ with $\alpha = (2, 2)$, $\beta = (4, 0)$ and $\gamma = (0, 3)$, and let $\Lambda = \{\lambda_1, \lambda_2\}$ where $\lambda_1 = (3, -1)$ and $\lambda_2 = (-3, 3)$. Then \mathcal{V}_Λ^1 consists of $(r, 1-r)$ for all $r \in [\frac{1}{4}, \frac{1}{2}]$. α is a compromise between the other two alternatives, and it minimises max D^k -relative regret; for $k \in \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$, $MRR_A^{D^k}(\alpha; \mathcal{V}_\Lambda^1)$ has values $\frac{1}{2}$, $\frac{1}{5}$, $\frac{1}{9}$ and $\frac{1}{13}$, respectively.

In more detail, we have $\bar{A} = (4, 3)$, $\underline{A} = (0, 0)$ and $\hat{A} = (2, \frac{5}{3})$. Let $u = (\frac{1}{4}, \frac{3}{4})$ and $v = (\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2})$. We have $u \cdot \alpha = 2$ and $u \cdot \beta = 1$, and $Val_A(u) = u \cdot \gamma = \frac{9}{4}$, so $R_A^u(\alpha) = \frac{1}{4}$. Also $Wor_A(u) = u \cdot \beta = 1$. We have $Val_A(v) = v \cdot \beta = v \cdot \alpha = 2$, so $R_A^v(\alpha) = 0$. Thus, for each $k \in \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$, $RR_A^{D^k}(\alpha; v) = 0$; and $MRR_A^{D^k}(\alpha; \mathcal{V}_\Lambda^1) = RR_A^{D^k}(\alpha; u) = R_A^u(\alpha)/D_A^k(u) = 1/(4D_A^k(u))$. We have $MR_A(\alpha; \mathcal{V}_\Lambda^1) = R_A^u(\alpha) = \frac{1}{4}$, and

$$D_A^3(u) = u \cdot (\bar{A} - \underline{A}) = u \cdot \bar{A} = \frac{13}{4}, \text{ so } MRR_A^{D^3}(\alpha; \mathcal{V}_\Lambda^1) = \frac{1}{13}.$$

$$D_A^2(u) = Val_A(u) = \frac{9}{4} \text{ so } MRR_A^{D^2}(\alpha; \mathcal{V}_\Lambda^1) = \frac{1}{9}.$$

$$D_A^1(u) = Val_A(u) - Wor_A(u) = \frac{9}{4} - 1 = \frac{5}{4}, \text{ so } MRR_A^{D^1}(\alpha; \mathcal{V}_\Lambda^1) = \frac{1}{5}.$$

$$D_A^0(u) = \frac{9}{4} - u \cdot \hat{A} = \frac{1}{2}, \text{ so } MRR_A^{D^0}(\alpha; \mathcal{V}_\Lambda^1) = \frac{1}{2}.$$

For β and γ we may need to consider non-extreme points of \mathcal{V}_Λ^1 . Let $w_r = (r, 1-r)$. Then $w_r \cdot \alpha = 2$, $w_r \cdot \beta = 4r$, and $w_r \cdot \gamma = 3-3r$.

Now, $w_r \cdot \alpha \geq w_r \cdot \beta \iff r = \frac{1}{2}$. For all $r \in [\frac{1}{4}, \frac{1}{2}]$, we have $w_r \cdot \alpha \geq w_r \cdot \beta$. $w_r \cdot \alpha \geq w_r \cdot \gamma \iff r = \frac{1}{3}$. For all $r \in [\frac{1}{4}, \frac{1}{3}]$, we have $w_r \cdot \alpha \leq w_r \cdot \gamma$, and for $r \in [\frac{1}{3}, \frac{1}{2}]$, $w_r \cdot \alpha \geq w_r \cdot \gamma$. Hence, $Val_A(w_r) = w_r \cdot \gamma$ for $r \in [\frac{1}{4}, \frac{1}{3}]$ and $Val_A(w_r) = w_r \cdot \alpha$ for $r \in [\frac{1}{3}, \frac{1}{2}]$.

$w_r \cdot \beta \geq w_r \cdot \gamma \iff r = \frac{3}{7}$. For all $r \in [\frac{1}{4}, \frac{3}{7}]$, we have $w_r \cdot \beta \leq w_r \cdot \gamma$, and for $r \in [\frac{3}{7}, \frac{1}{2}]$, $w_r \cdot \beta \geq w_r \cdot \gamma$. Hence, $Wor_A(w_r) = w_r \cdot \beta$ for $r \in [\frac{1}{4}, \frac{3}{7}]$ and $Wor_A(w_r) = w_r \cdot \gamma$ for $r \in [\frac{3}{7}, \frac{1}{2}]$.

A ratio of linear functions of x of the form $\frac{a+bx}{c+dx}$ is maximised over a closed interval at one of the endpoints of the interval; this can be seen by writing the function as $\frac{b}{d} + \frac{a-\frac{bc}{d}}{c+dx}$. For $k \in \{0, 2, 3\}$ and $\theta \in A$, $RR_A^{D^k}(\theta; w_r) = R_A^u(\theta)/D_A^k(w_r)$ is a ratio of linear functions of r within the intervals $[\frac{1}{4}, \frac{1}{3}]$ and $[\frac{1}{3}, \frac{1}{2}]$, so one only needs to check the three values $\frac{1}{4}$, $\frac{1}{3}$ and $\frac{1}{2}$ of r to find the maximum value of $RR_A^{D^k}(\theta; w_r)$, i.e., $MRR_A^{D^k}(\theta; \mathcal{V}_\Lambda^1)$. For $k = 1$ and $\theta \in A$, one needs to also consider the value $r = \frac{3}{7}$. Computations for these values of r lead to values of max D^k -relative regret given in Table 1.

$MRR_A^{D^k}(\theta; \mathcal{V}_\Lambda^1)$	$\theta = \alpha$	β	γ
$k = 0$	$\frac{1}{2}$	3	3
$k = 1$	$\frac{1}{5}$	1	1
$k = 2$	$\frac{1}{9}$	$\frac{5}{9}$	$\frac{1}{4}$
$k = 3$	$\frac{1}{13}$	$\frac{5}{13}$	$\frac{1}{7}$
$MR_A(\theta; \mathcal{V}_\Lambda^1)$	$\frac{1}{4}$	$\frac{5}{4}$	$\frac{1}{2}$

Table 1. Summary of values of max D^k -relative regret and max regret in Example 3.

5 Translation-Invariance

As discussed in Section 2.2, max regret satisfies translation-invariance, which means that the max regret is unchanged if we add a constant vector to each alternative in A . Because of this, the objective scales need only be interval scales (rather than ratio scales). We show here that max D^k -relative regret is translation-invariant for each of the four values of k .

We say that MRR^D is translation-invariant if for all finite $A \subseteq \mathbb{R}^p$ and $\alpha \in A$ and all $\delta \in \mathbb{R}^p$ and $\mathcal{W} \subseteq \mathbb{R}_+^p$, $MRR_{A+\delta}^D(\alpha + \delta; \mathcal{W}) = MRR_A^D(\alpha; \mathcal{W})$.

We consider an associated property for elements of \mathcal{D} : we say, for $D \in \mathcal{D}$, that D is translation-invariant if for all finite $A \subseteq \mathbb{R}^p$ and all $\delta \in \mathbb{R}^p$, and $w \in \mathbb{R}_+^p$, $D_{A+\delta}(w) = D_A(w)$. This will turn out to be a sufficient condition for translation-invariance of MRR^D that is satisfied by D^0, \dots, D^3 .

We say that a real-valued function $F_A(w)$ of w depending also on A translates with dot product if for all $\delta \in \mathbb{R}^p$ we always have $F_{A+\delta}(w) = F_A(w) + w \cdot \delta$.

The next lemma shows that the five basic families of functions in Proposition 7 all translate with dot product.

Lemma 4. Let \mathcal{A} be the set of all finite subsets A of \mathbb{R}^p . Consider a family of functions $\{F_A : A \in \mathcal{A}\}$ which is defined in one of the following ways:

- (I) for each finite $A \subseteq \mathbb{R}^p$ and $w \in \mathbb{R}_{>}^p$, $F_A(w) = \text{Val}_A(w)$; or
- (II) for each finite $A \subseteq \mathbb{R}^p$ and $w \in \mathbb{R}_{>}^p$, $F_A(w) = \text{Wor}_A(w)$; or
- (III) for each finite $A \subseteq \mathbb{R}^p$ and $w \in \mathbb{R}_{>}^p$, $F_A(w) = w \cdot \underline{A}$; or
- (IV) for each finite $A \subseteq \mathbb{R}^p$ and $w \in \mathbb{R}_{>}^p$, $F_A(w) = w \cdot \hat{A}$; or
- (V) for each finite $A \subseteq \mathbb{R}^p$ and $w \in \mathbb{R}_{>}^p$, $F_A(w) = w \cdot \bar{A}$.

Then F translates with dot product.

Proof: We have $\text{Val}_{A+\delta}(w) = \max_{\beta+\delta \in A+\delta} w \cdot (\beta + \delta) = \max_{\beta \in A} w \cdot \beta + w \cdot \delta = \text{Val}_A(w) + w \cdot \delta$. Similarly, $\text{Wor}_{A+\delta}(w) = \min_{\beta+\delta \in A+\delta} w \cdot (\beta + \delta) = \min_{\beta \in A} w \cdot \beta + w \cdot \delta = \text{Wor}_A(w) + w \cdot \delta$.

Let $B = A + \delta$. Then $\underline{B} = \underline{A} + \delta$, and so $w \cdot \underline{B} = w \cdot \underline{A} + w \cdot \delta$, showing that the function $w \cdot \underline{A}$ translates with dot product. Similarly, $\bar{B} = \bar{A} + \delta$ and $\hat{B} = \hat{A} + \delta$, so the functions $w \cdot \hat{A}$ and $w \cdot \bar{A}$ translate with dot product. \square

The functions $\text{Val}_A(w)$, $\text{Wor}_A(w)$, $w \cdot \underline{A}$, $w \cdot \hat{A}$ and $w \cdot \bar{A}$ all translate with dot product. A difference between two functions that translate with dot product is translation-invariant, because the two $w \cdot \delta$ terms cancel out. This implies that D^k is translation-invariant for each $k \in \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$.

Because $\text{Val}_A(w)$ translates with dot product, and $w \cdot (\alpha + \delta) = w \cdot \alpha + w \cdot \delta$, it follows that for any $w \in \mathbb{R}_{>}^p$, $R_{A+\delta}^w(\alpha + \delta) = R_A^w(\alpha)$, which leads to the following implication.

Proposition 10. If $D \in \mathcal{D}$ is translation-invariant then MRR^D is translation-invariant.

Proof: We have $\text{Val}_{A+\delta}(w) = \max_{\beta+\delta \in A+\delta} w \cdot (\beta + \delta) = \max_{\beta \in A} w \cdot \beta + w \cdot \delta = \text{Val}_A(w) + w \cdot \delta$. So, $R_{A+\delta}^w(\alpha + \delta) = \text{Val}_{A+\delta}(w) - w \cdot (\alpha + \delta) = \text{Val}_A(w) + w \cdot \delta - w \cdot \alpha - w \cdot \delta = \text{Val}_A(w) - w \cdot \alpha = R_A^w(\alpha)$. Then, for all $w \in \mathbb{R}_{>}^p$, $\text{RR}_{A+\delta}^D(\alpha + \delta; w) = \frac{R_{A+\delta}^w(\alpha + \delta)}{D_{A+\delta}(w)}$, which, by translation-invariance of D is equal to $\frac{R_A^w(\alpha)}{D_A(w)}$, i.e., $\text{RR}_A^D(\alpha; w)$; hence, $\text{MRR}_{A+\delta}^D(\alpha + \delta; \mathcal{W}) = \text{MRR}_A^D(\alpha; \mathcal{W})$. \square

Thus, by Proposition 10, we have:

Theorem 11. For all $k \in \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$, MRR^{D^k} satisfies translation-invariance.

6 Scale-Invariance

As discussed in Sections 1 and 2, a significant weakness of max regret is its lack of scale-invariance, i.e., invariance to relabelling the scales. Here we show that our four versions of max D^k -relative regret are scale-invariant.

We focus on the case where the set of weights vectors is of the form $\mathcal{V}_\Lambda \cap \mathcal{U}$, the intersection of a preference cone based on input vectors Λ with a preference-vacuous set \mathcal{U} . As discussed in Section 2.3, changing the scales of the objectives involves a strictly positive vector $\tau \in \mathbb{R}_{>}^p$, where each element γ of $A \cup \Lambda$ gets rewritten as $\gamma \odot \tau$, and $\mathcal{V}_\Lambda \cap \mathcal{U}$ becomes $\mathcal{V}_{\Lambda \odot \tau} \cap \mathcal{U}$. For $D \in \mathcal{D}$ we therefore define that MRR^D is scale-invariant if for each $\Lambda \subseteq \mathbb{R}^p$, for every preference-vacuous $\mathcal{U} \subseteq \mathbb{R}_{>}^p$, and any finite $A \subseteq \mathbb{R}^p$, and any $\alpha \in A$, and any $\tau \in \mathbb{R}_{>}^p$, we have $\text{MRR}_{A \odot \tau}^D(\alpha \odot \tau; \mathcal{V}_{\Lambda \odot \tau} \cap \mathcal{U}) = \text{MRR}_A^D(\alpha; \mathcal{V}_\Lambda \cap \mathcal{U})$.

Because of the conic closure property (Theorem 3), and the fact that $\mathcal{V}_{\Lambda \odot \tau} = \mathcal{V}_\Lambda \odot \tau^{-1}$, the above condition is equivalent to just $\text{MRR}_{A \odot \tau}^D(\alpha \odot \tau; \mathcal{V}_\Lambda \odot \tau^{-1}) = \text{MRR}_A^D(\alpha; \mathcal{V}_\Lambda)$.

Lemma 5. For $D \in \mathcal{D}$ we have that MRR^D is scale-invariant if and only if for each $\Lambda \subseteq \mathbb{R}^p$, for every preference-vacuous $\mathcal{U} \subseteq \mathbb{R}_{>}^p$, and any finite $A \subseteq \mathbb{R}^p$, and any $\alpha \in A$, and any $\tau \in \mathbb{R}_{>}^p$, $\text{MRR}_{A \odot \tau}^D(\alpha \odot \tau; \mathcal{V}_\Lambda \odot \tau^{-1}) = \text{MRR}_A^D(\alpha; \mathcal{V}_\Lambda)$.

Proof: If MRR^D is scale-invariant then $\text{MRR}_{A \odot \tau}^D(\alpha \odot \tau; \mathcal{V}_\Lambda \odot \tau^{-1}) = \text{MRR}_A^D(\alpha; \mathcal{V}_\Lambda)$, by using $\mathcal{U} = \mathbb{R}_{>}^p$, which is preference-vacuous.

For the converse, assume that $\text{MRR}_{A \odot \tau}^D(\alpha \odot \tau; \mathcal{V}_\Lambda \odot \tau^{-1}) = \text{MRR}_A^D(\alpha; \mathcal{V}_\Lambda)$, and consider arbitrary preference-vacuous \mathcal{U} ; it is sufficient to show that $\text{MRR}_{A \odot \tau}^D(\alpha \odot \tau; \mathcal{V}_{\Lambda \odot \tau} \cap \mathcal{U}) = \text{MRR}_A^D(\alpha; \mathcal{V}_\Lambda \cap \mathcal{U})$ and $\text{MRR}_A^D(\alpha; \mathcal{V}_\Lambda \cap \mathcal{U}) = \text{MRR}_A^D(\alpha; \mathcal{V}_\Lambda)$, since this then implies that $\text{MRR}_{A \odot \tau}^D(\alpha \odot \tau; \mathcal{V}_{\Lambda \odot \tau} \cap \mathcal{U}) = \text{MRR}_A^D(\alpha; \mathcal{V}_\Lambda \cap \mathcal{U})$.

Because \mathcal{V}_Λ is a cone and because \mathcal{U} is preference-vacuous, we have $\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{V}_\Lambda \cap \mathcal{U}) = \mathcal{V}_\Lambda$, using Lemma 1; similarly, we have $\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{V}_{\Lambda \odot \tau} \cap \mathcal{U}) = \mathcal{V}_{\Lambda \odot \tau}$, which equals $\mathcal{V}_\Lambda \odot \tau^{-1}$ by Lemma 2(i). The conic closure property (Theorem 3) then implies that $\text{MRR}_A^D(\alpha; \mathcal{V}_\Lambda \cap \mathcal{U}) = \text{MRR}_A^D(\alpha; \mathcal{V}_\Lambda)$ and $\text{MRR}_{A \odot \tau}^D(\alpha \odot \tau; \mathcal{V}_{\Lambda \odot \tau} \cap \mathcal{U}) = \text{MRR}_{A \odot \tau}^D(\alpha \odot \tau; \mathcal{V}_\Lambda \odot \tau^{-1})$, as required. \square

Let D be a family of functions $\{D_A\}$ parameterised by each finite subset A of \mathbb{R}^p , with each D_A being a real-valued function on $\mathbb{R}_{>}^p$. We say that D is scale-invariant if, for all A and w , and for all $\tau \in \mathbb{R}_{>}^p$, $D_{A \odot \tau}(w \odot \tau^{-1}) = D_A(w)$. We will show that this is a sufficient condition for scale-invariance of MRR^D that is satisfied by D^k , $k = 0, 1, 2, 3$.

For any $\tau \in \mathbb{R}_{>}^p$, for any $w \in \mathbb{R}_{>}^p$ and any $\gamma \in A$, $(w \odot \tau^{-1}) \cdot (\gamma \odot \tau) = w \cdot \gamma$. Being built from dot products, the functions $\text{Val}_A(w)$, $\text{Wor}_A(w)$, $w \cdot \underline{A}$, $w \cdot \hat{A}$ and $w \cdot \bar{A}$ are all scale-invariant, which implies that the functions D_A^k (for $k \in \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$) as differences of these, are all scale-invariant.

Lemma 6. Let \mathcal{A} be the set of all finite subsets A of \mathbb{R}^p . Consider a family of functions $\{F_A : A \in \mathcal{A}\}$ which is defined in one of the following ways:

- (I) for each finite $A \subseteq \mathbb{R}^p$ and $w \in \mathbb{R}_{>}^p$, $F_A(w) = \text{Val}_A(w)$; or
- (II) for each finite $A \subseteq \mathbb{R}^p$ and $w \in \mathbb{R}_{>}^p$, $F_A(w) = \text{Wor}_A(w)$; or
- (III) for each finite $A \subseteq \mathbb{R}^p$ and $w \in \mathbb{R}_{>}^p$, $F_A(w) = w \cdot \underline{A}$; or
- (IV) for each finite $A \subseteq \mathbb{R}^p$ and $w \in \mathbb{R}_{>}^p$, $F_A(w) = w \cdot \hat{A}$;
- (V) for each finite $A \subseteq \mathbb{R}^p$ and $w \in \mathbb{R}_{>}^p$, $F_A(w) = w \cdot \bar{A}$.

Then F satisfies scale-invariance.

Proof: For $\tau \in \mathbb{R}_{>}^p$, $w \in \mathbb{R}_{>}^p$ and $\gamma \in A$, $(w \odot \tau^{-1}) \cdot (\gamma \odot \tau) = w \cdot \gamma$. $\text{Val}_{A \odot \tau}(w \odot \tau^{-1}) = \max_{\beta \in A} (w \odot \tau^{-1}) \cdot (\beta \odot \tau) = \max_{\beta \in A} w \cdot \beta = \text{Val}_A(w)$. Thus in case (I), F satisfies scale-invariance. Case (II) is similar: $\text{Wor}_{A \odot \tau}(w \odot \tau^{-1}) = \min_{\beta \in A} (w \odot \tau^{-1}) \cdot (\beta \odot \tau) = \min_{\beta \in A} w \cdot \beta = \text{Wor}_A(w)$.

Let $B = A \odot \tau$. Then, for $i \in \{1, \dots, p\}$ we have $\underline{B}(i) = \min_{\alpha \in A} (\alpha \odot \tau)(i) = \min_{\alpha \in A} \alpha(i) \tau(i) = \tau(i) \min_{\alpha \in A} \alpha(i)$, (because $\tau(i) > 0$), which equals $\underline{A}(i) \tau(i) = (\underline{A} \odot \tau)(i)$; thus, $\underline{B} = \underline{A} \odot \tau$. Similarly, $\bar{B} = \bar{A} \odot \tau$ and $\hat{B} = \hat{A} \odot \tau$. Then, $(w \odot \tau^{-1}) \cdot \underline{B} = (w \odot \tau^{-1}) \cdot (\underline{A} \odot \tau) = w \cdot \underline{A}$, and similarly, $(w \odot \tau^{-1}) \cdot \bar{B} = w \cdot \bar{A}$ and $(w \odot \tau^{-1}) \cdot \hat{B} = w \cdot \hat{A}$, proving scale-invariance for cases (III), (IV) and (V). \square

Proposition 12. For $k \in \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$, D^k satisfies scale-invariance.

Proof: Each D^k is a difference between functions that are scale-invariant, and so is scale-invariant. For, instance, $D_A^1 = \text{Val}_A(w) -$

$Wor_A(w)$, and so $D_{A \odot \tau}^1(w \odot \tau^{-1}) = Val_{A \odot \tau}(w \odot \tau^{-1}) - Wor_{A \odot \tau}(w \odot \tau^{-1}) = Val_A(w) - Wor_A(w) = D_A^1(w)$. \square

Since $R_{A \odot \tau}^{w \odot \tau^{-1}}(\alpha \odot \tau) = R_A^w(\alpha)$, we have that scale-invariance of D is a sufficient condition for scale-invariance of MRR^D :

Proposition 13. *If D is scale-invariant then MRR^D is scale-invariant.*

Proof: Because D is scale-invariant and, by Lemma 2(iii), $R_{A \odot \tau}^{w \odot \tau^{-1}}(\alpha \odot \tau) = R_A^w(\alpha)$, we have for all $w \in \mathcal{V}$, $RR_{A \odot \tau}^D(\alpha \odot \tau; w \odot \tau^{-1}) = RR_A^D(\alpha; w)$. Taking the supremum over $w \in \mathcal{V}$ of both sides gives $MRR_{A \odot \tau}^D(\alpha \odot \tau; \mathcal{V} \odot \tau^{-1}) = MRR_A^D(\alpha; \mathcal{V})$, which, using Lemma 5, proves that MRR^D is scale-invariant. \square

From Proposition 12 and Proposition 13 we obtain scale-invariance for max D^k -relative regret.

Theorem 14. *For all $k \in \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$, MRR^{D^k} satisfies scale-invariance.*

If one rescales the objectives to make $\bar{A} - \underline{A} = \mathbf{1}$ and normalises a cone then this does not affect max D^k -relative regret. Considering the particular case of $k = 3$, max D^3 -relative regret is equal to max regret on the new scales. This is because for $w \in (\mathcal{V} \odot \sigma)^1$, where $\sigma = \bar{A} - \underline{A}$, we have $D_{A \odot \sigma^{-1}}^3(w) = w \cdot (\sigma \odot \sigma^{-1}) = w \cdot \mathbf{1} = 1$.

Proposition 15. *Let $\sigma = \bar{A} - \underline{A}$, assume that A is such that $\sigma(i) > 0$ for all $i \in \{1, \dots, p\}$, and let $\tau = \sigma^{-1}$. Then for any cone $\mathcal{V} \subseteq \mathbb{R}_{\geq}^p$, $MRR_A^{D^3}(\alpha; \mathcal{V})$ equals $MRR_{A \odot \tau}^{D^3}(\alpha \odot \tau; (\mathcal{V} \odot \sigma)^1) = MR_{A \odot \tau}(\alpha \odot \tau; (\mathcal{V} \odot \sigma)^1)$.*

Proof: Theorem 14 (scale invariance) implies $MRR_A^{D^3}(\alpha; \mathcal{V}) = MRR_{A \odot \tau}^{D^3}(\alpha \odot \tau; \mathcal{V} \odot \tau^{-1})$, which, using the conic closure property (Theorem 3) equals $MRR_{A \odot \tau}^{D^3}(\alpha \odot \tau; (\mathcal{V} \odot \tau^{-1})^1)$ because $\mathcal{C}((\mathcal{V} \odot \tau^{-1})^1) = \mathcal{V} \odot \tau^{-1}$.

Let $B = A \odot \tau$. Then $\bar{B} = \bar{A} \odot \tau$ and $\underline{B} = \underline{A} \odot \tau$, and $\bar{B} - \underline{B} = (\bar{A} - \underline{A}) \odot \tau = \mathbf{1}$. Thus, for any $w \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq}^p$, $D_{A \odot \tau}^3(w) = w \cdot (\bar{B} - \underline{B}) = w \cdot \mathbf{1}$. So, for any $w \in (\mathcal{V} \odot \tau^{-1})^1$ we have $D_{A \odot \tau}^3(w) = 1$ which implies $RR_{A \odot \tau}^{D^3}(\alpha; w) = R_{A \odot \tau}^w(\alpha)$ and so $MRR_{A \odot \tau}^{D^3}(\alpha \odot \tau; (\mathcal{V} \odot \tau^{-1})^1) = MR_{A \odot \tau}(\alpha \odot \tau; (\mathcal{V} \odot \tau^{-1})^1)$. \square

7 Convex Hull and Computation using Extreme Points

For $\mathcal{W} \subseteq \mathbb{R}_{\geq}^p$, its convex hull $CH(\mathcal{W})$ is the unique smallest convex set containing \mathcal{W} , and consists of all convex combinations (i.e., weighted means) of finite subsets of \mathcal{W} . If one replaces a set of user preference vectors \mathcal{W} by its convex hull $CH(\mathcal{W})$ then max regret is unchanged i.e., $MR_A(\alpha; \mathcal{W}) = MR_A(\alpha; CH(\mathcal{W}))$, which leads to $MR_A(\alpha; Ext(\mathcal{U})) = MR_A(\alpha; \mathcal{U})$, when \mathcal{U} is a convex polytope (such as \mathcal{V}_Λ^1 for finite Λ), enabling computation based on its extreme points $Ext(\mathcal{U})$ [17, 9, 18]. This convex closure property, however, does not always hold for max D -relative regret (or for max relative regret), as the example below shows. However it does hold for D^2 , D^3 and for some cases of D^0 ; and for the other cases and for D^1 , a more complex extreme point approach can be used, as shown in Theorem 17 below.

Example relating to failure of convex closure property

Let $p = 2$ and let $A = \{\alpha, \beta, \delta\}$ where $\alpha = (2c, -(1+c))$, $\beta = (-3c, 1)$, $\delta = (c, c)$, where $0 < c < 1$. We use $D = D^0$ for this example, and the mean \bar{A} of these three alternatives is $(0, 0)$; thus, $RR_A^D(\gamma; w) = \frac{Val_A(w) - w_r \cdot \gamma}{Val_A(w)}$ for any $w \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq}^2$ and any $\gamma \in A$; hence, the max D -relative regret is equal to the max relative regret. Consider the set $\mathcal{W} = \{w_r : r \in [0, 1]\}$, where $w_r = (r, 1-r)$, which is the convex hull of the set of extreme points $E = \{(1, 0), (0, 1)\}$. For any $r \in [0, 1]$ we have $w_r \cdot \alpha = r(1+3c) - (1+c)$ and $w_r \cdot \beta = 1 - r(1+3c)$, and $w_r \cdot \delta = c$.

We have $RR_A^D(\alpha; w_1) = 0$ since α is optimal when $r = 1$. With $r = 0$, β is optimal (since $c < 1$), and $Val_A(w_0) = (0, 1) \cdot \beta = 1$ and $w_0 \cdot \alpha = -(1+c)$, and so the D -relative regret $RR_A^D(\alpha; w_1)$ equals $2 + c$. This is thus the max D -relative regret $MRR_A^D(\alpha; E)$ based on the set of extreme points. However, putting $r = \frac{1-c}{1+3c}$ leads to a higher D -relative regret. We have $w_r \cdot \beta = c = w_r \cdot \delta$. Also, $w_r \cdot \alpha = -2c$, giving a D -relative regret of α of $\frac{3c}{c} = 3$, and in fact this is the maximum D -relative regret of α , so $MRR_A^D(\alpha; CH(E)) = 3 > 2 + c = MRR_A^D(\alpha; E)$.

In more detail: for $w_r = (r, 1-r) \in \mathcal{W}$, with $r \in [0, 1]$ we have

$$w_r \cdot (\beta - \alpha) = 2 + c - 2r(1+3c) = 2(1 + c/2 - r(1+3c)).$$

As we increase r from 0 until $\frac{1-c}{1+3c}$, the alternative β continues being optimal. During this interval in which β is optimal, the D -relative regret of α is $\frac{w_r \cdot (\beta - \alpha)}{w_r \cdot \beta}$, which equals $2 \frac{1+c/2-r(1+3c)}{1-r(1+3c)}$, which is increasing in r . This continues until $r = \frac{1-c}{1+3c}$ when $w_r \cdot \beta = w_r \cdot \delta = c$. At this point we have $w_r \cdot \alpha = \frac{1-c}{1+3c}(1+3c) - (1+c) = -2c$.

Increasing r from this point we have the D -relative regret of α being $\frac{c - w_r \cdot \alpha}{c}$, which decreases until zero when we have $w_r \cdot \alpha = c$. This happens when $r(1+3c) - (1+c) = c$, i.e., $r = \frac{1+2c}{1+3c}$.

In summary the maximum D -relative regret of α happens when $r = \frac{1-c}{1+3c}$, with value of D -relative regret of $\frac{c - w_r \cdot \alpha}{c} = \frac{c - (-2c)}{c} = 3$.

Like for max regret, it is possible to compute max D -relative regret using extreme points of convex polytopes; however, because of the more complex form of D -relative regret, it is a little more complicated. The basis is the following general result, giving a sufficient condition for invariance under convex closure. This condition uses the concept of a *quasi-convex* function on a convex set $\mathcal{W} \subseteq \mathbb{R}_{\geq}^p$, which is a real-valued function f such that for all real s , the set $\{w \in \mathcal{W} : f(w) \leq s\}$ is a convex set. In particular, any convex function, such as a maximum of linear functions, is also quasi-convex.

Theorem 16. *Let \mathcal{W} be a subset of \mathbb{R}_{\geq}^p . Let $r = MRR_A^D(\alpha; \mathcal{W}) \geq 0$, and define, for $w \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq}^p$, $g_r(w) = \bar{R}_A^w(\alpha) - rD_A(w)$, and suppose that g_r is a quasi-convex function on $CH(\mathcal{W})$, the convex hull of \mathcal{W} . Then, defining $Ext(\mathcal{W})$ to be the set of extreme points of \mathcal{W} ,*

- (i) $MRR_A^D(\alpha; CH(\mathcal{W})) = MRR_A^D(\alpha; \mathcal{W})$.
- (ii) If \mathcal{W} is convex and compact then $MRR_A^D(\alpha; \mathcal{W})$ is equal to $MRR_A^D(\alpha; Ext(\mathcal{W}))$.

Before giving the full proof, we give a proof sketch.

Proof Sketch: (i) Because of Proposition 4 (monotonicity), it is sufficient to show that $MRR_A^D(\alpha; CH(\mathcal{W})) \leq r$. Now, r is equal to $\sup_{w \in \mathcal{W}} RR_A^D(\alpha; w)$, so, for all $w \in \mathcal{W}$, $R_A^w(\alpha) \leq rD_A(w)$ and thus, $\sup_{w \in \mathcal{W}} g_r(w) \leq 0$. Quasi-convexity of g_r on $CH(\mathcal{W})$ implies that $\sup_{w \in CH(\mathcal{W})} g_r(w) = \sup_{w \in \mathcal{W}} g_r(w)$, and so

$\sup_{w \in CH(\mathcal{W})} g_r(w) \leq 0$ which implies $MRR_A^D(\alpha; CH(\mathcal{W})) \leq r$. Regarding (ii), we have $\mathcal{W} = CH(Ext(\mathcal{W}))$, and so (ii) follows by applying part (i) to $Ext(\mathcal{W})$. \square

As well as Lemma 3, we make use of the next lemma in the proof of Theorem 16.

Lemma 7. *Let \mathcal{W} be a subset of $\mathbb{R}_>^p$, and suppose that g is a quasi-convex function on $CH(\mathcal{W})$, the convex hull of \mathcal{W} . Then, $\sup_{w \in CH(\mathcal{W})} g(w) = \sup_{w \in \mathcal{W}} g(w)$.*

Proof: Let $s = \sup_{w \in \mathcal{W}} g(w)$. By quasi-convexity, the set $\mathcal{W}' = \{w \in CH(\mathcal{W}) : g(w) \leq s\}$ is convex; since \mathcal{W}' contains \mathcal{W} it also contains $CH(\mathcal{W})$, so $\mathcal{W}' = CH(\mathcal{W})$. This implies that $\sup_{w \in CH(\mathcal{W})} g(w) = \sup_{w \in \mathcal{W}} g(w)$. \square

Proof of Theorem 16: (i) Lemma 3 implies that $\sup_{w \in \mathcal{W}} g_r(w) \leq 0$, which, by Lemma 7, implies $\sup_{w \in CH(\mathcal{W})} g_r(w) \leq 0$, and thus we have $MRR_A^D(\alpha; CH(\mathcal{W})) \leq r$, using Lemma 3 again, i.e., $MRR_A^D(\alpha; CH(\mathcal{W})) \leq MRR_A^D(\alpha; \mathcal{W})$. Monotonicity (Proposition 4) implies $MRR_A^D(\alpha; CH(\mathcal{W})) \geq MRR_A^D(\alpha; \mathcal{W})$ so we have $MRR_A^D(\alpha; CH(\mathcal{W})) = MRR_A^D(\alpha; \mathcal{W})$.

(ii): Because \mathcal{W} is compact and convex, we have that $\mathcal{W} = CH(Ext(\mathcal{W}))$, and so (ii) follows by applying part (i) to $Ext(\mathcal{W})$. \square

For $t \geq 0$, define, for $w \in \mathbb{R}_>^p$, $g_t(w) = R_A^w(\alpha) - tD_A(w)$. With $D = D^3$, we have, for all $t \geq 0$ and $w \in \mathbb{R}_>^p$, $g_t(w) = Val_A(w) - w \cdot (\alpha + t(\bar{A} - \underline{A}))$, which is a convex and thus, a quasi-convex, function on any convex subset of $\mathbb{R}_>^p$. Theorem 16 then implies, for compact and convex \mathcal{W} , that $MRR_A^D(\alpha; \mathcal{W}) = MRR_A^D(\alpha; E)$, where E is the set $Ext(\mathcal{W})$ of extreme points of \mathcal{W} .

Now consider D_A of the form $Val_A(w) - w \cdot \theta$ for some $\theta \in \mathbb{R}^p$ (which may depend on A). This includes the cases D_A^2 and D_A^0 . Then $g_t(w) = (1-t)Val_A(w) - w \cdot (\alpha - t\theta)$, which is a convex (and hence quasi-convex) function when $t \leq 1$. We have $MRR_A^D(\alpha; E) \leq 1$ if and only if $MRR_A^D(\alpha; \mathcal{W}) \leq 1$ if and only if for all $w \in \mathcal{W}$, $w \cdot (\alpha - \theta) \geq 0$. Theorem 16 implies that if for all $w \in \mathcal{W}$, $w \cdot (\alpha - \theta) \geq 0$ then $MRR_A^D(\alpha; \mathcal{W}) = MRR_A^D(\alpha; E)$. This always holds for D^2 , and holds for D^0 if the utility $w \cdot \alpha$ of α is always at least as much as the mean element \hat{A} .

For D^1 and the more general case of D^0 , using the decomposition property (Proposition 5), \mathcal{W} can be split into parts for which the associated functions g_t are quasi-convex. For instance, with D^1 , for each $\gamma \in A$, we can consider of region \mathcal{W}_γ of \mathcal{W} in which γ is the worst element (so that $Wor_A(w) = w \cdot \gamma$ in that region), and then $g_t(w) = (1-t)Val_A(w) - w \cdot (\alpha - t\gamma)$, which is convex for all $t \leq 1$. By Theorem 9, $MRR_A^{D^1}(\alpha; \mathcal{W}_\gamma) \leq 1$, and so $g_t(w)$ is convex on \mathcal{W}_γ for $t = MRR_A^{D^1}(\alpha; \mathcal{W}_\gamma)$. Theorem 16 then implies $MRR_A^{D^1}(\alpha; \mathcal{W}_\gamma) = MRR_A^{D^1}(\alpha; Ext(\mathcal{W}_\gamma))$.

The next result gives one method for computing $MRR_A^{D^k}(\alpha; \mathcal{V})$, for $k \in \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ (with another, linear programming approach being given in Section 9). The proof is based on Theorem 16, using the fact that the function g_t (given by $g_t(w) = R_A^w(\alpha) - tD_A(w)$) is convex in \mathcal{V}^1 for $t \leq 1$ for $k = 0, 2, 3$. For $k = 2, 3$ we have $MRR_A^{D^k}(\alpha; \mathcal{V}) \leq 1$ which leads to a simpler condition. For $k = 1$, we need to divide up into sets of the form $\mathcal{V}^1[A \geq \gamma]$ (defined below) for g_t to be a convex function.

Let $\beta, \gamma \in A$. We define $\mathcal{V}^1[\beta \geq A]$ to be the set of all $w \in \mathcal{V}$ such that (i) $w \cdot \mathbf{1} = 1$, and (ii) $w \cdot \beta \geq w \cdot \alpha$ for all $\alpha \in A$. And we define $\mathcal{V}^1[A \geq \gamma]$ to be the set of $w \in \mathcal{V}$ such that $w \cdot \mathbf{1} = 1$

and for all $\alpha \in A$, $w \cdot \alpha \geq w \cdot \gamma$. Thus, $\mathcal{V}^1 = \bigcup_{\beta \in A} \mathcal{V}^1[\beta \geq A] = \bigcup_{\gamma \in A} \mathcal{V}^1[A \geq \gamma]$. For $\alpha, \theta \in \mathbb{R}^p$ we say that α dominates θ in \mathcal{W} , written $\alpha \succ_{\mathcal{W}} \theta$, to mean for all $w \in \mathcal{W}$, $w \cdot (\alpha - \theta) \geq 0$.

Theorem 17. *Let A be a finite subset of \mathbb{R}^p , and consider any $\alpha \in A$. Let $\mathcal{V} \subseteq \mathbb{R}_>^p$ be a topologically closed convex cone. Let $E = Ext(\mathcal{V}^1)$, $E' = \bigcup_{\beta \in A} Ext(\mathcal{V}^1[\beta \geq A])$ and $E'' = \bigcup_{\gamma \in A} Ext(\mathcal{V}^1[A \geq \gamma])$. Then we have*

$$\begin{aligned} MRR_A^{D^1}(\alpha; \mathcal{V}) &= MRR_A^{D^1}(\alpha; E''); \\ MRR_A^{D^2}(\alpha; \mathcal{V}) &= MRR_A^{D^2}(\alpha; E); \\ MRR_A^{D^3}(\alpha; \mathcal{V}) &= MRR_A^{D^3}(\alpha; E); \\ MRR_A^{D^0}(\alpha; \mathcal{V}) &= MRR_A^{D^0}(\alpha; E'). \\ \text{If } \alpha \succ_{\mathcal{V}} \hat{A} \text{ then } MRR_A^{D^0}(\alpha; \mathcal{V}) &= MRR_A^{D^0}(\alpha; E). \end{aligned}$$

Proof: First, observe that for each $k \in \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$, $MRR_A^{D^k}(\alpha; \mathcal{V}) = MRR_A^{D^k}(\alpha; \mathcal{V}^1)$, by the conic closure property (Theorem 3), because $\mathcal{V} = \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{V}^1)$. Next, note that \mathcal{V}^1 is compact and convex, being the intersection of the closed convex set \mathcal{V} with a compact convex set. (It is compact because it is a closed subset of a compact set, being closed because it is the intersection of closed sets.) Similarly, $\mathcal{V}^1[\beta \geq A]$ and $\mathcal{V}^1[A \geq \gamma]$ are compact and convex for all $\beta, \gamma \in A$.

For $t \geq 0$ define the function g_t by $g_t(w) = R_A^w(\alpha) - tD_A(w)$. We consider the simpler cases first.

The case of D_A^3 : For every $w \in \mathcal{V}$, $D_A^3(w) = w \cdot (\bar{A} - \underline{A})$, and so here $g_t(w) = R_A^w(\alpha) - tw \cdot (\bar{A} - \underline{A}) = Val_A(w) - w \cdot (\alpha + t\bar{A} - t\underline{A})$, which equals $\max_{\beta \in A} w \cdot (\beta - \alpha - t\bar{A} + t\underline{A})$, and so is a maximum of linear functions, and thus is a convex (and hence, quasi-convex) function on \mathcal{V}^1 for all $t \geq 0$. Theorem 16(ii) then implies that $MRR_A^{D^3}(\alpha; E) = MRR_A^{D^3}(\alpha; \mathcal{V}^1)$, which equals $MRR_A^{D^3}(\alpha; \mathcal{V})$, as observed at the beginning of the proof.

The case of D_A^2 : For D_A^2 we have $D_A^2(w) = Val_A(w) - w \cdot \underline{A}$ and thus, $g_t(w) = (1-t)Val_A(w) - w \cdot (\alpha - t\underline{A})$, which is convex on \mathcal{V}^1 for all t with $0 \leq t \leq 1$. We also have $MRR_A^{D^2}(\alpha; \mathcal{V}) \leq 1$, by Theorem 9. Hence, using Theorem 16(ii), $MRR_A^{D^2}(\alpha; \mathcal{V}) = MRR_A^{D^2}(\alpha; E)$.

The case of D_A^0 : we have $D_A^0(w) = Val_A(w) - w \cdot \hat{A}$ and thus, $g_t(w) = (1-t)Val_A(w) - w \cdot (\alpha - t\hat{A})$, which is convex on \mathcal{V}^1 for all t with $0 \leq t \leq 1$. Thus, by Theorem 16 if $MRR_A^{D^0}(\alpha; \mathcal{V}) \leq 1$ then $MRR_A^{D^0}(\alpha; \mathcal{V}) = MRR_A^{D^0}(\alpha; E)$. If $\alpha \succ_{\mathcal{V}} \hat{A}$ then for all $w \in \mathcal{V}$, $w \cdot \alpha \geq w \cdot \hat{A}$ which implies that $RR_A^{D^0}(\alpha; v) \leq 1$ and hence, $MRR_A^{D^0}(\alpha; \mathcal{V}) \leq 1$, and so we have $MRR_A^{D^0}(\alpha; \mathcal{V}) = MRR_A^{D^0}(\alpha; E)$.

Also, for each $\beta \in A$, on $\mathcal{V}[\beta \geq A]$ we have $g_t(w) = w \cdot ((1-t)\beta - \alpha + t\hat{A})$, which is a linear and hence a quasi-convex function on $\mathcal{V}^1[\beta \geq A]$ for all $t \geq 0$. Hence, by Theorem 16, for all $\beta \in A$, $MRR_A^{D^0}(\alpha; \mathcal{V}^1[\beta \geq A]) = MRR_A^{D^0}(\alpha; Ext(\mathcal{V}^1[\beta \geq A]))$. The decomposition property (Proposition 5) then implies that $MRR_A^{D^0}(\alpha; \mathcal{V}^1) = MRR_A^{D^0}(\alpha; E')$.

The case of D_A^1 : we have $D_A^1(w) = Val_A(w) - Wor_A(w)$ and thus, for each $\gamma \in A$, we have that $g_t(w) = (1-t)Val_A(w) - w \cdot (\alpha - t\gamma)$ on $\mathcal{V}^1[A \geq \gamma]$, which is a convex and hence quasi-convex function for all t with $0 \leq t \leq 1$. By Theorem 9, $MRR_A^{D^1}(\alpha; \mathcal{V}^1[A \geq \gamma]) \leq 1$, so, by Theorem 16, for each $\gamma \in A$, $MRR_A^{D^1}(\alpha; \mathcal{V}^1[A \geq \gamma]) = MRR_A^{D^1}(\alpha; Ext(\mathcal{V}^1[A \geq \gamma]))$. Then, using Proposition 5 (decomposition), $MRR_A^{D^1}(\alpha; \mathcal{V}^1) = MRR_A^{D^1}(\alpha; E'')$. \square

This last result, along with Proposition 8 and Theorem 9, implies the following corollary, that for $k \in \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$, the maximum D^k -relative regret values are finite and are attained within \mathcal{V}_Λ .

Corollary 18. *Consider any finite input preference set $\Lambda \subseteq \mathbb{R}^p$, any finite $A \subseteq \mathbb{R}^p$, and any alternative $\alpha \in A$, and any $k \in \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$. There exists $v \in \mathcal{V}_\Lambda$ such that $MRR_A^{D^k}(\alpha; \mathcal{V}_\Lambda) = RR_A^{D^k}(\alpha; v)$, so $MRR_A^{D^k}(\alpha; \mathcal{V}_\Lambda) = \max_{w \in \mathcal{V}_\Lambda} RR_A^{D^k}(\alpha; w)$. Furthermore, $MRR_A^{D^k}(\alpha; \mathcal{V}_\Lambda)$ is finite.*

Proof: Consider any $k \in \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$, and let $\mathcal{V} = \mathcal{V}_\Lambda$. Proposition 8 states that $D^k \in \mathcal{D}$, and Proposition 2 then implies that $MRR_A^{D^k}(\alpha; \mathcal{V}_\Lambda) \geq 0$. The sets E, E' and E'' in Theorem 17 are all finite, because the sets $\mathcal{V}^1, \mathcal{V}^1[\beta \geq A]$ and $\mathcal{V}^1[A \geq \gamma]$ are all compact polytopes and subsets of \mathcal{V} . Thus, Theorem 17 implies that $MRR_A^{D^k}(\alpha; \mathcal{V}_\Lambda) = RR_A^{D^k}(\alpha; v)$ for some $v \in E \cup E' \cup E'' \subseteq \mathcal{V}$, showing the first part. The last part of Proposition 8 implies that $RR_A^{D^k}(\alpha; v)$ is finite, and hence $MRR_A^{D^k}(\alpha; \mathcal{V}_\Lambda)$ is finite. \square

8 Relationships between MRR and MR

Each weights vector w can be viewed as converting the scales of the different objectives to a value of utility. Thus, $w \cdot \alpha$ is a value of utility, and may be considered to be a number of *utiles* (i.e., units of utility). Then $Val_A(w)$ is a number of utiles, and $R_A^w(\alpha)$ and hence $MR_A(\alpha; \mathcal{W})$ can be considered as having units of utiles. The values $D_A(w)$, in particular, the values $D_A^k(w)$ defined in Section 4, also have units of utiles. D -relative regret and max D -relative regret are thus ratios of utiles, and so are unit-free. This means that max regret and max D -relative regret are not fully comparable, and one cannot expect all the same properties.

However when D_A does not vary much over the set \mathcal{W} , in particular, if \mathcal{W} is a very small set (which may happen towards the end of an interactive optimisation session), then the ratio of values of max D -relative regret will be similar to the ratios of the corresponding values of max regret, as we show in Section 8.1.

In contrast, in Section 8.2, we constrain the set of weights vectors to satisfy $D_A(w) = 1$, and then max D -relative regret is the same as max regret; this leads to the linear programming approach for computation described in Section 9.

8.1 Bounding the ratio of MR and MRR

Proposition 19 bounds the ratio of max regret and max D -relative regret in terms of the minimum and maximum values of D_A .

Proposition 19. *For $\alpha \in A$ such that $\alpha \notin \text{NO}_{\mathcal{W}}(A)$, we have*

$$\inf_{w \in \mathcal{W}} D_A(w) \leq \frac{MR_A(\alpha; \mathcal{W})}{MRR_A^D(\alpha; \mathcal{W})} \leq \sup_{w \in \mathcal{W}} D_A(w).$$

Proof: The assumptions imply (by Proposition 2) that we have $MRR_A^D(\alpha; \mathcal{W}) > 0$. Let L equal $\inf_{w \in \mathcal{W}} D_A(w)$ and let U equal $\sup_{w \in \mathcal{W}} D_A(w)$.

Regarding the upper bound inequality, this is satisfied if $MRR_A^D(\alpha; \mathcal{W}) = \infty$, so we can assume that $MRR_A^D(\alpha; \mathcal{W})$ is finite, and thus, $RR_A^D(\alpha; w)$ is finite for all $w \in \mathcal{W}$. Then we have that $D_A(w)RR_A^D(\alpha; w)$ equals $R_A^w(\alpha)$, and so, $MR_A(\alpha; \mathcal{W}) = \sup_{w \in \mathcal{W}} R_A^w(\alpha) = \sup_{w \in \mathcal{W}} D_A(w)RR_A^D(\alpha; w) \leq$

$U \sup_{w \in \mathcal{W}} RR_A^D(\alpha; w)$ which is equal to $U \times MRR_A^D(\alpha; \mathcal{W})$. Hence, $\frac{MR_A(\alpha; \mathcal{W})}{MRR_A^D(\alpha; \mathcal{W})} \leq U$.

Regarding the lower bound inequality, first note that this holds trivially if $L = \inf_{w \in \mathcal{W}} D_A(w) = 0$. So let us consider the case where $L > 0$. Then for all $w \in \mathcal{W}$ we have $D_A(w) \geq L > 0$, and so $\frac{1}{D_A(w)} \leq \frac{1}{L}$. Thus, $RR_A^D(\alpha; w) = \frac{R_A^w(\alpha)}{D_A(w)} \leq \frac{R_A^w(\alpha)}{L}$, so $MRR_A^D(\alpha; \mathcal{W}) = \sup_{w \in \mathcal{W}} \frac{R_A^w(\alpha)}{D_A(w)} \leq \frac{1}{L} \sup_{w \in \mathcal{W}} R_A^w(\alpha) = \frac{1}{L} MR_A(\alpha; \mathcal{W})$, and thus, $L \leq \frac{MR_A(\alpha; \mathcal{W})}{MRR_A^D(\alpha; \mathcal{W})}$. \square

The next result illustrates that, using diminishing \mathcal{W} , the ratio of the max D -relative regret of two alternatives tends to the limit of the ratio for max regret. In particular, for small sets \mathcal{W} , the way that max regret and max D -relative regret order alternatives will tend to be similar.

Proposition 20. *For $v \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq}^p$ and real $\epsilon > 0$ let $\mathcal{N}_\epsilon(v)$ be all $w \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq}^p$ such that for all $i \in \{1, \dots, p\}$, $|w(i) - v(i)| \leq \epsilon$. Assume that D_A is continuous, and that $D_A(v) > 0$, and $\alpha, \beta \in A$ where $R_A^v(\alpha) > 0$. For any $\mathcal{W} \subseteq \mathbb{R}_{\geq}^p$ containing v let $\mathcal{W}_\epsilon^v = \mathcal{W} \cap \mathcal{N}_\epsilon(v)$. Then,*

$$\lim_{\epsilon \rightarrow 0} \frac{MRR_A^D(\beta; \mathcal{W}_\epsilon^v)}{MRR_A^D(\alpha; \mathcal{W}_\epsilon^v)} = \frac{R_A^v(\beta)}{R_A^v(\alpha)} = \lim_{\epsilon \rightarrow 0} \frac{MR_A(\beta; \mathcal{W}_\epsilon^v)}{MR_A(\alpha; \mathcal{W}_\epsilon^v)}.$$

Proof: For arbitrary $\gamma \in A$ we will show in the next paragraphs that $\lim_{\epsilon \rightarrow 0} MR_A(\gamma; \mathcal{W}_\epsilon^v) = R_A^v(\gamma)$, and that $\lim_{\epsilon \rightarrow 0} MRR_A^D(\gamma; \mathcal{W}_\epsilon^v) = \frac{R_A^v(\gamma)}{D_A(v)}$. Then, since this implies $\lim_{\epsilon \rightarrow 0} MRR_A^D(\alpha; \mathcal{W}_\epsilon^v) > 0$, we have $\lim_{\epsilon \rightarrow 0} \frac{MRR_A^D(\beta; \mathcal{W}_\epsilon^v)}{MRR_A^D(\alpha; \mathcal{W}_\epsilon^v)} = \frac{\lim_{\epsilon \rightarrow 0} MRR_A^D(\beta; \mathcal{W}_\epsilon^v)}{\lim_{\epsilon \rightarrow 0} MRR_A^D(\alpha; \mathcal{W}_\epsilon^v)}$, which is equal to $\frac{R_A^v(\beta)}{R_A^v(\alpha)}$. Similarly, $\lim_{\epsilon \rightarrow 0} \frac{MR_A(\beta; \mathcal{W}_\epsilon^v)}{MR_A(\alpha; \mathcal{W}_\epsilon^v)} = \frac{\lim_{\epsilon \rightarrow 0} MR_A(\beta; \mathcal{W}_\epsilon^v)}{\lim_{\epsilon \rightarrow 0} MR_A(\alpha; \mathcal{W}_\epsilon^v)}$, which equals $\frac{R_A^v(\beta)}{R_A^v(\alpha)}$.

For any $\epsilon > 0$, the set \mathcal{W}_ϵ^v contains v , and so $MRR_A^D(\gamma; \mathcal{W}_\epsilon^v) \geq RR_A^D(\gamma; v) = \frac{R_A^v(\gamma)}{D_A(v)}$. Now, consider any $s > 0$. We will show that there exists $\epsilon > 0$ such that $MRR_A^D(\gamma; \mathcal{W}_\epsilon^v) \leq \frac{R_A^v(\gamma)}{D_A(v)} + s$; since $MRR_A^D(\gamma; \mathcal{W}_\epsilon^v) \leq MRR_A^D(\gamma; \mathcal{W}_\epsilon^v)$ if $0 < \epsilon' \leq \epsilon$ this then implies $\lim_{\epsilon \rightarrow 0} MRR_A^D(\gamma; \mathcal{W}_\epsilon^v) = \frac{R_A^v(\gamma)}{D_A(v)}$.

Because D_A is continuous and $D_A(v) > 0$, there exists a neighbourhood of v such that $D_A(w) > 0$ for all w in this neighbourhood, and then continuity of $R_A^w(\gamma)$ with respect to w implies that $RR_A^D(\gamma; w)$ is continuous within this neighbourhood. So there exists some $\epsilon > 0$ such that for all $w \in \mathcal{W}_\epsilon^v$, we have $RR_A^D(\gamma; w) \leq \frac{R_A^v(\gamma)}{D_A(v)} + s$; this implies $MRR_A^D(\gamma; \mathcal{W}_\epsilon^v) \leq \frac{R_A^v(\gamma)}{D_A(v)} + s$, as required. The same argument also works to show $\lim_{\epsilon \rightarrow 0} MR_A(\gamma; \mathcal{W}_\epsilon^v) = R_A^v(\gamma)$. \square

8.2 When $D_A = 1$, MRR equals MR

We next will show how max D -relative regret can be expressed in terms of max regret on a different preference space, by considering preference vectors w such that $D_A(w) = 1$. Let us write for cone $\mathcal{V} \subseteq \mathbb{R}_{\geq}^p$,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{V}[D_A = 0] &= \{w \in \mathcal{V} : D_A(w) = 0\}, \text{ and similarly,} \\ \mathcal{V}[D_A = 1] &= \{w \in \mathcal{V} : D_A(w) = 1\} \text{ and} \\ \mathcal{V}[D_A > 0] &= \{w \in \mathcal{V} : D_A(w) > 0\}. \end{aligned}$$

We can split \mathcal{V} into $\mathcal{V}[D_A = 0]$ and $\mathcal{V}[D_A > 0]$, and deal with the two separately, because of Proposition 5 (decomposition). The case of $\mathcal{V}[D_A = 0]$ is somewhat trivial, and follows from Proposition 2:

Proposition 21. $MRR_A^D(\alpha; \mathcal{V}[D_A = 0]) = 0$ if and only if $\alpha \in \text{NO}_{\mathcal{V}[D_A=0]}(A)$, i.e., if α is optimal in A with respect to every $w \in \mathcal{V}$ such that $D_A(w) = 0$; otherwise, $MRR_A^D(\alpha; \mathcal{V}[D_A = 0]) = \infty$.

Proof: If $\alpha \in \text{NO}_{\mathcal{V}[D_A=0]}(A)$ then for all $w \in \mathcal{V}[D_A = 0]$ we have $R_A^w(\alpha) = 0$ and thus, $RR_A^D(\alpha; w) = 0$; this implies that $MRR_A^D(\alpha; \mathcal{V}[D_A = 0]) = 0$.

Now suppose that $\alpha \notin \text{NO}_{\mathcal{V}[D_A=0]}(A)$; then there exists $w \in \mathcal{V}[D_A = 0]$ such that $R_A^w(\alpha) > 0$ and then $RR_A^D(\alpha; w) = \infty$, which implies that $MRR_A^D(\alpha; \mathcal{V}[D_A = 0]) = \infty$. \square

For a cone $\mathcal{V} \subseteq \mathbb{R}_{\geq}^p$, and finite $A \subseteq \mathbb{R}^p$, and $\beta, \gamma \in A$, let $\mathcal{V}[\beta \geq A]$ be all $w \in \mathcal{V}$ such that $w \cdot \beta \geq w \cdot \alpha$ for all $\alpha \in A$, i.e., all w in the cone for which β is optimal in A . And let $\mathcal{V}[\beta \geq A \geq \gamma]$ be all $w \in \mathcal{V}$ such that $w \cdot \beta \geq w \cdot \alpha \geq w \cdot \gamma$ for all $\alpha \in A$, i.e., all w in the cone for which β is the best element in A , and γ is the worst. We then define $\mathcal{V}[D_A = 1; \beta \geq A]$ to consist of all $w \in \mathcal{V}[\beta \geq A]$ such that $D_A(w) = 1$; similarly, define $\mathcal{V}[D_A = 1; \beta \geq A \geq \gamma]$ to be the set of all $w \in \mathcal{V}[\beta \geq A \geq \gamma]$ such that $D_A(w) = 1$.

Theorem 22 shows how max D -relative regret is equivalent to max regret over a different set of preference models. It also shows how it can be expressed in terms of maximising a linear function, which will lead to LP solution methods for particular D (see Section 9).

Theorem 22. Let $\mathcal{V} \subseteq \mathbb{R}_{\geq}^p$ be a cone. If $\alpha \notin \text{NO}_{\mathcal{V}[D_A=0]}(A)$ then $MRR_A^D(\alpha; \mathcal{V}) = \infty$. Otherwise, if $\alpha \in \text{NO}_{\mathcal{V}[D_A=0]}(A)$, then $MRR_A^D(\alpha; \mathcal{V}) = MRR_A^D(\alpha; \mathcal{V}[D_A = 1]) = MR_A(\alpha; \mathcal{V}[D_A = 1])$, which equals $\max_{\beta \in A} \sup\{w \cdot (\beta - \alpha) : w \in \mathcal{V}[D_A = 1; \beta \geq A]\}$, and $\max_{\beta, \gamma \in A} \sup\{w \cdot (\beta - \alpha) : w \in \mathcal{V}[D_A = 1; \beta \geq A \geq \gamma]\}$.

As well as the proof below we give the following proof sketch.

Proof Sketch: Since $\mathcal{V} = \mathcal{V}[D_A = 0] \cup \mathcal{V}[D_A > 0]$, by Proposition 5, $MRR_A^D(\alpha; \mathcal{V})$ is the maximum of $MRR_A^D(\alpha; \mathcal{V}[D_A = 0])$ and $MRR_A^D(\alpha; \mathcal{V}[D_A > 0])$. The first part then follows using Proposition 21. Otherwise, if α is an element of $\text{NO}_{\mathcal{V}[D_A=0]}(A)$ then $MRR_A^D(\alpha; \mathcal{V}[D_A = 0])$ is equal to 0 so $MRR_A^D(\alpha; \mathcal{V}) = MRR_A^D(\alpha; \mathcal{V}[D_A > 0])$ which equals $MRR_A^D(\alpha; \mathcal{V}[D_A = 1])$ using Theorem 3 (conic closure), because $\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{V}[D_A = 1]) = \mathcal{V}[D_A > 0]$. For $w \in \mathcal{V}[D_A = 1]$ we have $RR_A^D(\alpha; w) = R_A^w(\alpha)$, and so $MRR_A^D(\alpha; \mathcal{V}[D_A = 1]) = MR_A(\alpha; \mathcal{V}[D_A = 1])$. Using Proposition 5 (Decomposition) this equals $\max_{\beta \in A} \sup\{w \cdot (\beta - \alpha) : w \in \mathcal{V}[D_A = 1; \beta \geq A]\}$, because for $w \in \mathcal{V}[D_A = 1; \beta \geq A]$ we have $RR_A^D(\alpha; w) = R_A^w(\alpha) = w \cdot (\beta - \alpha)$. The last part follows similarly. \square

Proof of Theorem 22

Note first that $\mathcal{V}[D_A > 0]$ is a cone, since if $w \in \mathcal{V}[D_A > 0]$ and $r > 0$ then $rw \in \mathcal{V}$ and $D_A(rw) = rD_A(w) > 0$ and so $rw \in \mathcal{V}[D_A > 0]$.

Clearly, $\mathcal{V}[D_A = 1] \subseteq \mathcal{V}[D_A > 0]$. This implies $\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{V}[D_A = 1]) \subseteq \mathcal{V}[D_A > 0]$, because the latter is a cone. Now consider any $w \in \mathcal{V}[D_A > 0]$, and let $v = \frac{w}{D_A(w)}$, which is in the cone \mathcal{V} since $w \in \mathcal{V}$. Then $D_A(v) = \frac{D_A(w)}{D_A(w)} = 1$, and so $v \in \mathcal{V}[D_A = 1]$, and therefore, $w \in \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{V}[D_A = 1])$. This shows that $\mathcal{V}[D_A > 0] \subseteq \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{V}[D_A = 1])$. We have shown that $\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{V}[D_A = 1]) = \mathcal{V}[D_A > 0]$.

Thus, by the conic closure theorem (Theorem 3), we have that $MRR_A^D(\alpha; \mathcal{V}[D_A > 0])$ is equal to $MRR_A^D(\alpha; \mathcal{V}[D_A = 1])$. By Proposition 5 we have

$$MRR_A^D(\alpha; \mathcal{V}) = \max(MRR_A^D(\alpha; \mathcal{V}[D_A = 0]), MRR_A^D(\alpha; \mathcal{V}[D_A > 0])),$$

which thus equals

$$\max(MRR_A^D(\alpha; \mathcal{V}[D_A = 0]), MRR_A^D(\alpha; \mathcal{V}[D_A = 1])).$$

If $\alpha \notin \text{NO}_{\mathcal{V}[D_A=0]}(A)$ then $MRR_A^D(\alpha; \mathcal{V}[D_A = 0]) = \infty$, by Proposition 21, and so $MRR_A^D(\alpha; \mathcal{V}) = \infty$.

If $\alpha \in \text{NO}_{\mathcal{V}[D_A=0]}(A)$ then, also by Proposition 21, we have $MRR_A^D(\alpha; \mathcal{V}[D_A = 0]) = 0$, and so $MRR_A^D(\alpha; \mathcal{V}) = MRR_A^D(\alpha; \mathcal{V}[D_A = 1])$, since it is non-negative. For $w \in \mathcal{V}[D_A = 1]$ we have $RR_A^D(\alpha; w) = R_A^w(\alpha)$, and so $MRR_A^D(\alpha; \mathcal{V}[D_A = 1]) = MR_A(\alpha; \mathcal{V}[D_A = 1])$.

Now, $\mathcal{V}[D_A = 1]$ is equal to $\bigcup_{\beta \in A} \mathcal{V}[D_A = 1; \beta \geq A]$. By the decomposition property (Proposition 5), $MRR_A^D(\alpha; \mathcal{V})$ then equals $\max_{\beta \in A} MRR_A^D(\alpha; \mathcal{V}[D_A = 1; \beta \geq A])$. For $w \in \mathcal{V}[D_A = 1; \beta \geq A]$ we have $R_A^w(\alpha) = \text{Val}_A(w) - w \cdot \alpha = w \cdot (\beta - \alpha)$, and $D_A(w) = 1$, so $RR_A^D(\alpha; w) = w \cdot (\beta - \alpha)$, and thus, $MRR_A^D(\alpha; \mathcal{V}[D_A = 1; \beta \geq A]) = \sup\{w \cdot (\beta - \alpha) : w \in \mathcal{V}[D_A = 1; \beta \geq A]\}$. Hence, $MRR_A^D(\alpha; \mathcal{V})$ equals $\max_{\beta \in A} \sup\{w \cdot (\beta - \alpha) : w \in \mathcal{V}[D_A = 1; \beta \geq A]\}$.

Regarding the final equality, we have that $\mathcal{V}[D_A = 1]$ is equal to $\bigcup_{\beta, \gamma \in A} \mathcal{V}[D_A = 1; \beta \geq A \geq \gamma]$, and so, by Proposition 5, $MRR_A^D(\alpha; \mathcal{V})$ equals $\max_{\beta, \gamma \in A} MRR_A^D(\alpha; \mathcal{V}[D_A = 1; \beta \geq A \geq \gamma])$, which is equal to

$$\max_{\beta, \gamma \in A} \sup\{w \cdot (\beta - \alpha) : w \in \mathcal{V}[D_A = 1; \beta \geq A \geq \gamma]\}.$$

\square

9 Computation using Linear Programming

For a cone $\mathcal{V} \subseteq \mathbb{R}_{\geq}^p$, and finite $A \subseteq \mathbb{R}^p$, and $\beta, \gamma \in A$, and $\psi \in \mathbb{R}^p$, let $\mathcal{V}^\psi[\beta \geq A]$ be the set of all $w \in \mathcal{V}[\beta \geq A]$ such that $w \cdot \psi = 1$; also, let $\mathcal{V}^\psi[\beta \geq A \geq \gamma]$ be the set of all $w \in \mathcal{V}[\beta \geq A \geq \gamma]$ such that $w \cdot \psi = 1$.

The following result is used in the proof of Theorem 23 below.

Lemma 8. Let \mathcal{V} be a cone. Then we have:

$$MRR_A^{D^0}(\alpha; \mathcal{V}) = \max_{\beta \in A} \sup\{w \cdot (\beta - \alpha) : w \in \mathcal{V}^{\beta - \hat{A}}[\beta \geq A]\}.$$

$$MRR_A^{D^1}(\alpha; \mathcal{V}) = \max_{\beta, \gamma \in A} \sup\{w \cdot (\beta - \alpha) : w \in \mathcal{V}^{\beta - \gamma}[\beta \geq A \geq \gamma]\}.$$

$$MRR_A^{D^2}(\alpha; \mathcal{V}) = \max_{\beta \in A} \sup\{w \cdot (\beta - \alpha) : w \in \mathcal{V}^{\beta - \underline{A}}[\beta \geq A]\}.$$

$$MRR_A^{D^3}(\alpha; \mathcal{V}) = \max_{\beta \in A} \sup\{w \cdot (\beta - \alpha) : w \in \mathcal{V}^{\bar{A} - \underline{A}}[\beta \geq A]\}.$$

Proof: Let k be any element of $\{0, 1, 2, 3\}$, and let $D = D^k$. Using Proposition 8, for any $w \in \mathcal{V}$ if $D_A^k(w) = 0$ then for all $\gamma \in A$, $R_A^w(\gamma) = 0$ and so $RR_A^D(\alpha; w) = 0$, and thus, $\text{NO}_{\mathcal{V}[D_A=0]}(A) = A$. Hence, by Theorem 22, $MRR_A^D(\alpha; \mathcal{V}) = \max_{\beta \in A} \sup\{w \cdot (\beta - \alpha) : w \in \mathcal{V}[D_A = 1; \beta \geq A]\}$. For $k = 0, 2$ or 3 , in the presence of the constraint $\beta \geq A$ enforcing that β is best alternative, the condition $D_A^k(w) = 1$ is a linear constraint of the form $w \cdot \psi_k = 1$, where $\psi_0 = \beta - \hat{A}$, $\psi_2 = \beta - \underline{A}$ and $\psi_3 = \bar{A} - \underline{A}$, and so $\mathcal{V}[D_A = 1; \beta \geq A]$ can be written as $\mathcal{V}^{\psi_k}[\beta \geq A]$. This proves the equalities for these three cases.

For the final case, D_A^1 , we use the last part of Theorem 22, showing that $MRR_A^D(\alpha; \mathcal{V}) = \max_{\beta, \gamma \in A} \sup\{w \cdot (\beta - \alpha) : w \in \mathcal{V}[D_A^1 = 1; \beta \geq A \geq \gamma]\}$. In the presence of the constraint labelled by $\beta \geq A \geq \gamma$, the constraint $D_A^1(w) = 1$ is a linear constraint $w \cdot (\beta - \gamma) = 1$, and so $\mathcal{V}[D_A^1 = 1; \beta \geq A \geq \gamma]$ is the same as $\mathcal{V}^{\beta - \gamma}[\beta \geq A \geq \gamma]$, proving the last equality. \square

The next result is the basis of a linear programming algorithm for computing max D -relative regret $MRR_A^{D^k}(\alpha; \mathcal{V})$, for any $k \in \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$, for a preference cone $\mathcal{V} = \mathcal{V}_\Lambda$. The proof of this is based on Theorem 22.

For $k = 0, 2$ or 3 , in the presence of the constraint $\beta \geq A$ enforcing that β is a best alternative (and so $Val_A(w) = w \cdot \beta$), the condition $D_A^k(w) = 1$ is a linear constraint of the form $w \cdot \psi_k = 1$, where $\psi_0 = \beta - \hat{A}$, $\psi_2 = \beta - \underline{A}$ and $\psi_3 = \bar{A} - \underline{A}$; hence, $\mathcal{V}[D_A = 1; \beta \geq A]$ can be written as $\mathcal{V}^{\psi_k}[\beta \geq A]$. For the final case, D_A^1 , we use the last part of Theorem 22. Given the constraint enforcing that β is the best and γ is the worst element of A , the constraint $D_A^1(w) = 1$ is a linear constraint $w \cdot (\beta - \gamma) = 1$, and so $\mathcal{V}[D_A^1 = 1; \beta \geq A \geq \gamma]$ is the same as $\mathcal{V}^{\beta-\gamma}[\beta \geq A \geq \gamma]$, leading to the corresponding equality.

Theorem 23. *Consider any finite input preference set $\Lambda \subseteq \mathbb{R}^p$, any finite $A \subseteq \mathbb{R}^p$, and $\alpha \in A$. Then $MRR_A^{D^k}(\alpha; \mathcal{V}_\Lambda)$ is finite for all $k \in \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$. In addition, abbreviating \mathcal{V}_Λ to \mathcal{V} , we have*

$$MRR_A^{D^0}(\alpha; \mathcal{V}) = \max_{\beta \in A} \max\{w \cdot (\beta - \alpha) : w \in \mathcal{V}^{\beta - \hat{A}}[\beta \geq A]\}.$$

$$MRR_A^{D^1}(\alpha; \mathcal{V}) = \max_{\beta, \gamma \in A} \max\{w \cdot (\beta - \alpha) : w \in \mathcal{V}^{\beta - \gamma}[\beta \geq A \geq \gamma]\}.$$

$$MRR_A^{D^2}(\alpha; \mathcal{V}) = \max_{\beta \in A} \max\{w \cdot (\beta - \alpha) : w \in \mathcal{V}^{\beta - \underline{A}}[\beta \geq A]\}.$$

$$MRR_A^{D^3}(\alpha; \mathcal{V}) = \max_{\beta \in A} \max\{w \cdot (\beta - \alpha) : w \in \mathcal{V}^{\bar{A} - \underline{A}}[\beta \geq A]\},$$

using the convention that the max of an empty set is equal to zero.

Proof: Corollary 18 implies that $MRR_A^{D^k}(\alpha; \mathcal{V}_\Lambda)$ is finite for all $k \in \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$. Lemma 8 shows each of the four equalities when the second max is replaced by sup; hence to complete the proof it is sufficient to show firstly, for arbitrary $\beta \in A$, for $k \in \{0, 2, 3\}$ there exists $w \in \mathcal{V}^{\psi_k(\beta)}[\beta \geq A]$ such that $w \cdot (\beta - \alpha) = \sup\{u \cdot (\beta - \alpha) : u \in \mathcal{V}^{\psi_k(\beta)}[\beta \geq A]\}$, i.e., the supremum is obtained, where $\psi_0(\beta) = \beta - \hat{A}$, $\psi_2(\beta) = \beta - \underline{A}$ and $\psi_3(\beta) = \bar{A} - \underline{A}$. Secondly, for arbitrary $\beta, \gamma \in A$, we need to show that there exists $w \in \mathcal{V}^{\beta-\gamma}[\beta \geq A \geq \gamma]$ such that $w \cdot (\beta - \alpha) = \sup\{u \cdot (\beta - \alpha) : u \in \mathcal{V}^{\beta-\gamma}[\beta \geq A \geq \gamma]\}$.

Consider $k \in \{0, 2, 3\}$. Applying Corollary 18 to the cone $\mathcal{V}[\beta \geq A]$, we obtain that there exists $v \in \mathcal{V}[\beta \geq A]$ such that $MRR_A^{D^k}(\alpha; \mathcal{V}[\beta \geq A]) = RR_A^{D^k}(\alpha; v)$.

If $v \cdot \psi_k(\beta) = 0$ then $D_A^k(v) = 0$ so $R_A^k(\alpha) = 0$ by Proposition 8, and thus, $RR_A^{D^k}(\alpha; v) = 0$, and hence, $MRR_A^{D^k}(\alpha; \mathcal{V}[\beta \geq A]) = 0$. Because $\mathcal{V}[\beta \geq A] \supseteq \mathcal{V}^{\psi_k(\beta)}[\beta \geq A]$ we have $MRR_A^{D^k}(\alpha; \mathcal{V}^{\psi_k(\beta)}[\beta \geq A]) = 0$, which implies that $w \cdot (\beta - \alpha) = 0$ for any $w \in \mathcal{V}^{\psi_k(\beta)}[\beta \geq A]$, so any such w attains the required supremum.

Since $v \cdot \psi_k(\beta) = D_A^k(v) \geq 0$, we can now assume that $v \cdot \psi_k(\beta) > 0$. Let $w = \frac{v}{v \cdot \psi_k(\beta)}$, which is a member of $\mathcal{V}^{\psi_k(\beta)}[\beta \geq A]$. Then, using Lemma 8 and the definition of v , we have $\sup\{u \cdot (\beta - \alpha) : u \in \mathcal{V}^{\psi_k(\beta)}[\beta \geq A]\} = MRR_A^{D^k}(\alpha; \mathcal{V}[\beta \geq A]) = RR_A^{D^k}(\alpha; v) = RR_A^{D^k}(\alpha; w)$, which, because $D_A^k(w) = 1$, equals $w \cdot (\beta - \alpha)$, as required.

The proof of the $k = 1$ part is similar. Applying Corollary 18 to the cone $\mathcal{V}[\beta \geq A \geq \gamma]$, we obtain that there exists $v \in \mathcal{V}[\beta \geq A \geq \gamma]$ such that $MRR_A^{D^1}(\alpha; \mathcal{V}[\beta \geq A \geq \gamma]) = RR_A^{D^1}(\alpha; v)$.

If $v \cdot (\beta - \gamma) = 0$ then $D_A(v) = 0$ so $R_A^1(\alpha) = 0$ by Proposition 8, and thus, $MRR_A^{D^1}(\alpha; \mathcal{V}[\beta \geq A \geq \gamma]) = RR_A^{D^1}(\alpha; v) =$

0 . Because $\mathcal{V}[\beta \geq A \geq \gamma] \supseteq \mathcal{V}^{\psi_1(\beta)}[\beta \geq A \geq \gamma]$ we have $MRR_A^{D^1}(\alpha; \mathcal{V}^{\psi_1(\beta)}[\beta \geq A \geq \gamma]) = 0$, which implies that $w \cdot (\beta - \alpha) = 0$ for any $w \in \mathcal{V}^{\psi_1(\beta)}[\beta \geq A \geq \gamma]$, so any such w attains the required supremum.

We can now assume $v \cdot (\beta - \gamma) \neq 0$, i.e., $v \cdot (\beta - \gamma) > 0$ (since $v \in \mathcal{V}[\beta \geq A \geq \gamma]$ implies $v \cdot (\beta - \gamma) \geq 0$). Let $w = \frac{v}{v \cdot (\beta - \gamma)}$, which is a member of $\mathcal{V}^{\beta-\gamma}[\beta \geq A \geq \gamma]$. Then, again using Lemma 8 and the definition of v , we have $\sup\{u \cdot (\beta - \alpha) : u \in \mathcal{V}^{\beta-\gamma}[\beta \geq A \geq \gamma]\} = MRR_A^{D^1}(\alpha; \mathcal{V}[\beta \geq A \geq \gamma]) = RR_A^{D^1}(\alpha; v) = RR_A^{D^1}(\alpha; w)$, which, because $D_A^1(w) = 1$, equals $w \cdot (\beta - \alpha)$, as required. \square

For a given set A of alternatives and set Λ of user preference inputs, let us consider the computation of the $|A|$ numbers $\{MRR_A^{D^k}(\alpha; \mathcal{V}_\Lambda) : \alpha \in A\}$, i.e., the function $MRR_A^{D^k}(\cdot; \mathcal{V}_\Lambda)$ over A . For $k = 3$, we can use the same LP computation method as for max regret, involving a total of $|A||A - 1|$ linear maximisation problems, each with $|\Lambda| + 1$ constraints. For $k = 0$ or 2 , Theorem 23 allows the computation of the full function with $|A||A - 1|$ linear maximisations, each with $|\Lambda| + |A|$ constraints (and, like the other problems, with $p - 1$ or p variables). With $k = 1$ the computation is slower, involving $|A||A - 1|^2$ linear maximisation problems, each with $|\Lambda| + 2|A| - 1$ constraints.

The extreme points method from Section 7 will not be computationally feasible if the number of extreme points is very large. Even for small Λ and moderate sized A , the sets E' and E'' will tend to be very large, since they are based on polytopes generated from $|\Lambda| + |A| + 1$ constraints. But, regarding the cases of $k = 2, 3$ (and the $k = 0$ case for any α that dominate \hat{A}), if there are only a fairly small number of user preferences Λ then the set E may well not be too large; once E is computed, the computation of the whole function is only $\mathcal{O}(p|E||A|^2)$ which can in such cases be faster than the LP algorithm.

10 Conclusions and Discussion

We have defined variations of max regret (see Section 4), that maintain key properties of max regret, but have the important advantage of being scale-invariant; this means that the values of max regret (and the relative ordering of alternatives) is not dependent on what can be a somewhat arbitrary choice of units of the objectives.

This gives a clearer meaning to the values, and one can use these variations in just the same way as max regret: for recommending a compromise alternative, that minimises the measure; for terminating a user interaction when the value of max D -relative regret of an alternative is close to zero; and for generating queries. In particular, the standard current solution strategy adapts simply: we can choose a query α versus β where α minimises max D -relative regret, and β is its worst adversary, being optimal in A with respect to the weights vector w that maximises $RR_A^D(\alpha; w)$, the D -relative regret for α .

One can consider other definitions of D apart from the four choices in Section 4. One class of functions is of the form $Val_A(w) - w \cdot \psi_A$, for $\psi_A \in \mathbb{R}^p$ depending on A . Families D^0 (with $\psi_A = \hat{A}$) and D^2 (with $\psi_A = \underline{A}$) are both of this form, but there are other reasonable choices as well, such as ψ_A being an average of \hat{A} and \underline{A} .

It would be interesting to extend the definition to setwise max regret and compare the properties with standard setwise max regret [21, 19].

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